

Understanding **THE** **S**elf

by Aaron Vranken |

*Four Modern Accounts of Self
and Personal Reflections*

UNDERSTANDING THE SELF

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*In memory of Camus.
(My cat, not the philosopher.)*

Table of Contents

INTRODUCTION

§1. What is the self?.....	5
§2. Summary of Contents.....	5

PART 1 MODERN ACCOUNTS OF SELF

Chapter 1 Descartes.....	11
§3. Introduction.....	11
§4. The Ego Cogito.....	12
§5. The Intuitive Self-Evidence of the Ego.....	18
Chapter 2 Locke.....	21
§6. Molyneux's Letter.....	21
§7. Discovering the Problem of Personal Identity.....	21
§8. Of Identity and Diversity.....	26
Chapter 3 Hume.....	35
§9. Real and Fictitious Ideas.....	35
§10. The Organic Fiction.....	38
§11. Penelhum's Objection.....	43
§12. The Appendix Aporia.....	45
§13. The Reflexivity of a Constructive Idea of Mind.....	50
Chapter 4 Kant.....	53
§14. Synthetic Judgements A Priori.....	53
§15. The Transcendental Deduction.....	56
§16. The Paralogisms.....	62
§17. Sensation and Experience.....	66

TABLE OF CONTENTS

PART 2 PERSONAL REFLECTIONS

Chapter 1 A Flat Ontology: The I and the Other.....77

§18. Introduction.....77

§19. The Pure Ego.....78

§20. The Inner and Outer.....80

§21. The I and the Other.....84

§22. Consequences for Personal Identity.....85

§23. Concluding Section.....89

BIBLIOGRAPHY

INTRODUCTION

Introduction

§1. What is the self?

Many of the problems in philosophy are treated for their own sake. We do not quite know why they are important, but in spite of ourselves, they are. We feel that they must have an answer and that this answer must have some value to ourselves or others. —*This is particularly true of the present paper. I do not know why, but for the past 4 years I've been very interested in the ideas of self and subjectivity in Western philosophy. This is not because I have an especially strong sense of what the self is or ought to be, rather I have none at all. Whenever philosophers talk about the self, soul, I, person, subject or consciousness, I hardly know what they are going on about. This simple question, 'What is the self?', I have so far been unable to answer in any straightforward or confident manner. With this paper, I wish to accomplish two things: On the one hand, to clarify (to a modest extent) the sense of the question that I am asking. To better understand what other philosophers mean by this concept and how I should interpret it. On the other, to formulate a provisional and unfinished answer.*

Of course, the self is an ambiguous term which can refer to a variety of different concepts. We can take it to mean the 'mind', which turns it into a metaphysical or epistemological problem; the 'I', which makes it a question about consciousness, subjectivity or reference; the 'me', which places us in the domain of psychology and sociology; or the 'person', which would have us explain the conditions (over time) of our being the particular person we are and not someone else. These varied distinctions in our meanings of the concept self will not always be clearly made in this paper. Mainly because I have taken modern philosophy as my starting point and these distinctions aren't yet explicitly made in most modern texts. To read these philosophers with this conceptual framework in mind, and to place each of their concepts of self neatly into these categories, would itself introduce more exegetical problems than I could solve in one thesis. Nevertheless, whenever such distinctions between different concepts of subjectivity are made by these philosophers, I will try to mark them clearly and show their place in their respective philosophies.

§2. Summary of Contents

This paper can be distinguished into two parts. In the first, I give interpretations of

four of the main theories of self and subjectivity in modern philosophy: those of Descartes, Locke, Hume and Kant. There are two reasons why I've chosen these philosophers. *On the one hand*, because the central role of the self in Western philosophy is often reputed to be the result of Descartes' use of the ego as an epistemological concept intended to ensure the *a priori* possibility of certain knowledge. The philosophies of Locke, Hume and Kant all develop, reinterpret and criticise these Cartesian foundations. *On the other*, because the rejection of the ego cogito in Lockean philosophy marks the reintroduction of the problem of personal identity in Western philosophy, and both the theories of Hume and Kant can be regarded as attempted solutions to this problem. As I can only discuss a few philosophers in a paper of this limited length, I believe that for the subject I'm interested in, this is a good selection.

Throughout these interpretations, I will engage with these different philosophers and criticise, continue or defend their arguments where needed. It is by means of these engagements that I wish to better understand the problem I'm dealing with and determine my own position. Wherever my interpretation deviates from the ordinary understanding of these philosophers, I will explicitly defend it against those put forward by other interpreters (e.g., §§4,8 and 12).

The chapters of the first part will be ordered chronologically, starting with chapter 1 on Descartes' idea of the ego cogito in the *Meditations*. He famously equates the I with mind as a cogitative substance whose primary function is to ensure the possibility of certain knowledge. I will argue that, contrary to popular belief, this ego is not a self-consciousness and does not entail a rejection of our embodied existence. In a personal section (§5), I will attempt to show that Descartes is mistaken in his belief in the ego cogito by arguing that the cogito does not actually imply the existence of the ego.

Chapter 2 deals with Locke's introduction of the problem of personal identity in modern philosophy. Due to his rejection of the Cartesian immaterial substance and because he separated the thought or cogito from the mind, he had to find another way to explain in what the continuity of a person's existence consists. His solution quite famously relies on the ideas of consciousness and memory. As noted by Allison, however, Locke's influence on the debate on personal identity was largely negative.¹ It didn't take long before detractors from varied philosophical traditions started pointing out (supposed) flaws in his arguments. Of the many critics I will concern myself solely with Thomas Reid and attempt a defence of Locke's theory of personal identity against Reid's objection(s). I will argue that what Locke proposes is not a simple memory theory and consequently that consciousness is not synonymous with remembrance and does not imply transitivity.

Chapter 3, on the self in Humean philosophy, is complicated by the fact that Hume

¹ Allison, 'Locke's Theory of Personal Identity', 41.

SUMMARY OF CONTENTS

rejects his own explanation of personal identity in the *Appendix* to the *Treatise*. As Hume imagined the self to be a natural fiction, I will begin by explaining what this term means and how it fits into his empiricist epistemology, before giving an account of how the fictitious identity of the self comes about. Though I will present multiple interpretations of the problem of the *Appendix*, I will not myself endorse any one of them as I believe that Hume does not give enough information to settle the matter one way or another. I've included two personal sections in this chapter. In the first (§11), I argue, relying on Penelhum's objection to Hume's theory of identity, that he needn't have regarded our attribution of numerical identity as the result of a psychological tendency to be continuously mistaken. In the second (§13), I claim that we should reject Galen Strawson's realist interpretation of Hume for epistemological reasons, whether it corresponds to Hume's actual intentions or not.

Chapter 4, finally, will deal with subjectivity in Kant's *Critique of Pure Reason*. Both the rationalist and empiricist ideas of self are given a place in his transcendental philosophy. The ego cogito returns under the form of the transcendental apperception, but Kant denies that this 'I think' can give us any knowledge of objective existences—the I is a purely logical unity which we must necessarily presuppose in order to explain the possibility of experience. And while we can have knowledge of the empirical self, it is always given to us as the object and never as the subject of experience. It is therefore never the 'I' of the 'I think'. In the final section of chapter 4 (§17), I criticise the Lockean, Humean and Kantian ideas of sensation and claim that if we do not believe in the existence of unitary and simple sensations, then there's no reason to presuppose the existence of the synthetic unity of apperception.

In the second part I make an (admittedly presumptuous) first attempt at figuring out what the self is and determining my own position in relation to the philosophers of the previous part. In §19, I will argue against the existence of a pure ego, this is a continuation of my arguments against Descartes and Kant in §§5 and 17 respectively. A rejection of the existence of 'inner phenomena', that is: experiences which are necessarily first-personal, is given in §20. What I wish to establish is that experience is in its first appearance impersonal. The remaining sections are dedicated to explaining why this matters to me (§21) and how this influences our thinking on personal identity (§22). I will not myself try to *solve* the problem of personal identity since I do not believe that any definite solution can be given. We should accept the same contingency of the self as we ordinarily do of other empirical objects and regard it simply as a classification which does not have a predestined correlate in external reality.

PART 1
MODERN ACCOUNTS OF SELF

Chapter 1

Descartes

§3. Introduction

Descartes, in his reply to the *Second Set of Objections* to the *Meditations*, stresses the importance of attention and careful contemplation in understanding his abstruse and often metaphysical arguments. He distinguishes two forms which an argument can take: *synthesis*, which is constructive, the agreed upon method of logic, geometry, the deductive sciences; which, in a series of consecutive statements, moves from definitions and axioms towards irrefutable conclusions; and *analysis*, what we might call a regressive approach, moving in the opposite direction, it is the way by which a science is first discovered and the validity of its premisses, its initial truth, can be established.¹ The *Meditations*, as the name implies, is thoroughly analytic. He remarks that analysis, though it allows the reader to understand something as if he had discovered it himself, cannot be used to teach someone who is inattentive or unwilling to consider the topic being discussed. It requires the reader's cooperation. Given all of this, it is regrettable that so few actually take the time to understand the *Meditations*. The criticisms of many of its detractors can be chalked up to a sloppy interpretation of the main text, or a disregard for its second part, the objections and replies, which should be treated as a necessary supplement to principal six meditations.²

My interpretation of Descartes' theory of self (§4) will focus on the ontological proof of the 'I' as found in the *Meditations*, in particular, the *Second Meditation, Concerning the Nature of the Human Mind: That It Is Better Known than the Body*. Though the arguments there presented will be well known to most philosophers, I have elected to set them out

¹ Descartes, *Meditations, Objections, and Replies*, 92.

² E.g., the objections voiced by J.B. Freeman in *Acceptable Premises: An Epistemic Approach to an Informal Logic Problem*, 5–9., criticising Descartes' foundationalism for being overly restrictive, can be easily refuted by quoting Antoine Arnauld's thoughtful remarks on Descartes' criterion of clear and distinct ideas: 'he is dealing only with things that pertain to the academic disciplines and that fall within the grasp of human understanding, he is not, however, dealing with matters of faith or the conduct of life.' (Descartes, *Meditations, Objections, and Replies*, 129.); directing his attention to the many occasions, in the objections and replies when Descartes' himself touches upon the different ways of knowing something (e.g. *Ibid.*, 88.); or the third paragraph of the *Principles* wherein he distinguishes the conditions of (certain) truth from those necessary for the conduct of daily life (Descartes, *Principles of Philosophy*, 3.).

in full, sticking closely to the form of the original, in order to maintain the analytic and organic nature which is, to my knowledge, the primary source of their clarity. I will occasionally refer to the *Discourse* or *Principles* to supplement or support my interpretation. The main discovery of the *Second Meditation* is the existence of the pure ego as the innermost core of subjectivity. In Descartes' case, this pure ego is an ego cogito, that is: a thinking thing. Though this cogitative self is largely rejected by Locke and Hume, it will make its return—in a somewhat modified form—in Kant's theory of the transcendental apperception (§15). Near the end of §4 I will argue, first, that this ego cogito does not imply a radical divide between mind and body, as is often claimed,¹ and; secondly, that it is not a consciousness in the sense of self-consciousness.

§4. *The Ego Cogito*

Yesterday's meditation has thrown me into such doubts that I can no longer ignore them, yet I fail to see how they are to be resolved. It is as if I had suddenly fallen into a deep whirlpool; I am so tossed about that I can neither touch bottom with my foot, nor swim up to the top.²

When we get to the *Second Meditation*, Descartes has already convinced himself that he is fallible creature: Many of the things he once thought to be true turned out to be false and he might yet discover himself to be mistaken in many of his present beliefs. Wishing to free himself of this perpetual uncertainty, and in hopes of discovering a sure foundation for his knowledge, he decides to methodically rid himself of all his presuppositions—everything that can be doubted, he treats as false. He famously invokes the idea of an evil genius or supremely powerful deceiver. Empirical perception is put out of play, as it is imagined to be an illusion conjured up by this deceiver, even mathematical knowledge is rejected—it being entirely possible that we are subtly misled every time we try to add, subtract, multiply or divide any two numbers.³ Accordingly, we suppose that everything we see is false, all the world is empty, there is earth nor sky, even the body and its sensations, its hunger or pain, are merely illusions. It is when attempting to doubt his own existence that Descartes makes his famous discovery:

'Is it then the case that I too do not exist? But doubtless I did exist, if I persuaded myself of something. But there is some deceiver or other who is supremely powerful and supremely sly and who is always deliberately deceiving me. Then too there is no doubt that I exist, if he is deceiving me.'⁴

1 Johnson, *The Meaning of the Body: Aesthetics of Human Understanding*, 3–4; Ryle, *The Concept of Mind*, 5; Williams, *Descartes: The Project of Pure Enquiry*.

2 Descartes, *Meditations, Objections, and Replies*, 13.

3 *Ibid.*, 9–13.

4 *Ibid.*, 13.

I may doubt and doubt hyperbolically, yet I cannot doubt that there is something which doubts; even if there is a supremely powerful deceiver, though perhaps deceived, I still exist. From the mere act of doubting (or thinking), knowledge of our own existence follows. We must be careful not to mistake this argument for a logical inference or syllogism. In his reply to the *Second Set of Objections*, Descartes notes: ‘in such a case [of a syllogism] we would have to know beforehand the major premiss (“whatever thinks is or exists”). But surely it is instead the case that he learns this by experiencing for himself that it is impossible for him to be thinking without existing.’¹ That is to say: we recognise the ‘*I am thinking therefore I exist*’² as intuitively self-evident.

I will argue in §5 that this appeal to intuition leaves Descartes open to the obvious objection—which amounts to a basic disagreement of fact—that the thought does not presuppose the thinker. In doubting or thinking, what is given is the doubt or thought, not the thing which doubts or thinks. In perceiving an object *x*, while I can doubt whether there exists anything resembling this object outside of perception, I cannot possibly doubt that there is a perception of *x*; but this perception does not necessarily involve an ‘I think *x*’.

The question of existence makes way for that of essence: granted that I exist, what is this I that exists?³ Descartes distinguishes two kinds of substance: mind and body. At this point in the text the distinction expresses nothing but a common way of speaking about things, it is only in the *Sixth Meditations* that the real distinction between mind and body is proved.⁴ Both concepts are defined in the *Reply to Second Set of Objections*:

‘That substance in which thought immediately resides is “mind.”’⁵

‘That substance which is the immediate subject of local extension and of the accidents that presuppose extension, such as shape, position, movement from place to place, and so on, is called “body.”’⁶

Most of the things we associate with ourselves—our sensations, appearance, physical acts—are related to the concept of body and might simply be illusions. Consequently, they cannot be essential to the self; the idea being that it is impossible to think an object whilst denying its essence. Though this thesis is at one time or another disputed in all objections, Descartes holds his ground. His argument is effectively summarised by Antoine Arnauld: ‘[E]ven if I were stubbornly to maintain that abso-

1 Descartes, *Meditations, Objections, and Replies*, 83.

2 Descartes, *A Discourse on the Method*, 29.

3 Descartes, *Meditations, Objections, and Replies*, 13.

4 *Ibid.*, 44.

5 *Ibid.*, 95.

6 *Ibid.*

lutely no bodies existed, nevertheless the thesis still stands: I am something. Therefore I am not a body.¹ Instead, Descartes argues that the only thing intrinsically related to the self is thought (*cogito*)—though I can deny myself most properties, thinking is the one thing I cannot do without. ‘[P]erhaps it could also come to pass that if I were to cease all thinking I would then utterly cease to exist.’² A corresponding passage in *Discourse* reads: ‘if I had merely ceased thinking, I would have no reason to believe that I existed, even if everything else I imagined had been true.’³ In short: it is the essence of the I to be a *thinking thing*, i.e., a mind. In fact, this attribute manages to exhaustively describe the I. If thought was used in the colloquial sense such a definition would certainly be too restrictive. By it we denote contemplation, reflection, often in relation to the imagination or abstract objects; Descartes, however, supplements this argument with an enumeration of different kinds of thought (presumably inexhaustive): ‘But what am I? A thing that thinks. What is that? A thing that doubts, understands, affirms, denies, wills, refuses, and that also imagines and senses.’⁴ Thought being the essence of the I, the latter are merely its modes.

The Cartesian *cogito* (or thought) is a very broad concept and does not refer to a certain species of perception or experience, but to a perspective from which any and every experience can be approached.

‘By the word “thought”, I understand all those things which occur in us while we are conscious, insofar as the consciousness of them is in us. And so not only understanding, willing, and imagining, but also sensing, are here the same as thinking. For if I say, I see, or I walk, therefore I am; and if I deduce this [conclusion] from seeing or from walking which is performed by the body; the conclusion is not absolutely certain [...] But if I deduce this from {the action of my mind, or} the very sensation of consciousness of seeing or of walking; the conclusion is completely certain, for it [the premise] then refers to the mind which alone perceives or thinks that it is seeing or walking.’⁵

I can look at any experience either as it relates to the object of this experience, and then it can certainly be false, or as it relates to my thinking or subjectively perceiving this object, and this is always beyond doubt. E.g. it is possible that there is nothing outside of perception which corresponds to pages in front of me, but nevertheless I cannot doubt that, regarded by itself, this perception exists.

The *Second Meditation* continues with Descartes’ beautifully succinct passage on the piece of wax, touching upon the problem of individuation and the distinction between

1 Descartes, *Meditations, Objections, and Replies*, 117.

2 Ibid., 15.

3 Descartes, *A Discourse on the Method*, 29.

4 Descartes, *Meditations, Objections, and Replies*, 15.

5 Descartes, *Principles of Philosophy*, 5–6.

substance and accident. His goals are twofold and interrelated: to reverse the preconception that bodies—that is to say: corporeal objects—are more easily known than the mind and to prove that of the many things we denote by ‘sensing’, most should actually be attributed to thought. It is also at this point in the text that the immediacy and certainty with which thoughts present themselves to the mind becomes apparent.

‘Let us take, for instance, this piece of wax. It has been taken quite recently from the honeycomb; it has not yet lost all the honey flavor. It retains some of the scent of the flowers from which it was collected. Its color, shape, and size are manifest. It is hard and cold; it is easy to touch. If you rap on it with your knuckle it will emit a sound. In short, everything is present in it that appears needed to enable a body to be known as distinctly as possible. But notice that, as I am speaking, I am bringing it close to the fire. The remaining traces of the honey flavor are disappearing; the scent is vanishing; the color is changing; the original shape is disappearing. Its size is increasing; it is becoming liquid and hot; you can hardly touch it. And now, when you rap on it, it no longer emits any sound. Does the same wax still remain?’¹

Descartes is playing at the naïve belief, held by most of us in daily life, that we perceive the object of our experiences in the same way that we perceive its properties. That, at the same time that we’re seeing the white of the wax, smelling its scent, we’re also seeing the wax itself, sensing it to be the selfsame wax in a succession of different perceptions. The above passage seeks to eliminate this presupposition. If there is no sensory property in the wax which remains constant throughout its changes, then its persistent identity cannot be a result of the senses. Instead, he claims, it is the mind which judges impressions to be certain objects.

‘But then were I perchance to look out my window and observe men crossing the square, I would ordinarily say I see the men themselves just as I say I see the wax. But what do I see aside from hats and clothes, which could conceal automata? Yet I judge them to be men. Thus what I thought I had seen with my eyes, I actually grasped solely with the faculty of judgement, which is my mind.’²

As noted by Wood,³ Descartes, more than a 100 years before the fact, appears on the verge of discovering an idealism resembling Kant’s. Instead, he hurriedly makes good on the second part of the chapter’s title, *That It [the mind] Is Better Known than the Body*, by concluding that—since perceiving is nothing but a form of judging, and judging is a property of the mind—any perception I may have only serves to further convince myself of my own existence.

The definition of the I as a thinking thing is both one of the most interesting aspects

1 Descartes, *Meditations, Objections, and Replies*, 16.

2 Ibid., 17–18.

3 Wood, ‘Descartes’ Philosophy of Mind’, 473.

of Descartes' philosophy and the most likely to mislead. We should remind ourselves that he is dealing with the I as an epistemological concept, a pure ego, the function of which is to ensure the possibility of certain knowledge. That this limited concept of self excludes all empirical properties should not be taken to mean that Descartes regarded man to be nothing but a cogitative being. In particular, we cannot attribute to him the view that man, in its actual existence, is a being radically divided into mind and body, of which the former has precedence over the latter. In the *Sixth Meditation* this is explicitly rejected:

'By means of pain, hunger, thirst, and so on, nature also teaches that I am present in my body not merely in the way a sailor is present in a ship, but that I am most tightly joined and, so to speak, commingled with it, so much so that I and the body constitute one single thing.'¹

This line of argument is taken up again in his reply to Antoine Arnauld's objections:

'[L]est anyone therefore think that man is merely "a soul using a body." For in the very same Sixth Meditation, where I dealt with the distinction between the mind and body, I also proved at the same time that the mind is substantially united to the body.'²

He goes on to elaborate on the difference between the mind and body, saying:

'And the person who claims that a man's arm is a substance really distinct from the rest of his body does not on that account deny that the arm belongs to the nature of the whole man; nor does the person who claims that the arm belongs to the nature of the whole man provide on that account any occasion for suspecting that it cannot subsist in its own right.'³

We should consider the relation between mind and body to be comparable to the relation between handle and brush. Though we can imagine each to exist separate from the other, in a broom they become substantially united. We can further imagine them to be joined with such force that neither of them can actually be separated from the other, yet still we are capable of regarding them as separate entities and perhaps even hypothesise the existence of a being capable of separating them in reality.

Neither can we attribute to Descartes, as is sometimes done,⁴ the invention of consciousness as self-consciousness. While our thoughts are immediately present to the mind, the mind is not a self-presence. That Descartes is not the 'inventor' of conscious-

1 Descartes, *Meditations, Objections, and Replies*, 45.

2 Ibid., 136.

3 Ibid.

4 Allison, 'Locke's Theory of Personal Identity', 44; Strawson, *The Evident Connexion*, 90; Shoemaker, 'Self-Knowledge and "Inner Sense": Lecture II: The Broad Perceptual Model', 271.

ness is one of the theses of Balibar's *Identity and Difference* with which I wholeheartedly agree.¹ Descartes hardly uses the word and when it does turn up, it is without its contemporary meaning. Besides, the self was never the principal subject of the *Meditations*. His proof of the ego, both its *that* and its *what*, are in function of his overarching search for certainty. Consciousness, or the self-reflexive ego, never becomes part of his investigation.

One of the passages mentioned by Balibar,² seems to contradict this thesis: 'For surely we cannot avoid always experiencing within ourselves that we think.'³ Considering, however, that this is the only occurrence of this idea, and secondly, that it is part of a rather harsh reply to the impolite *Sixth Set of Objections*, it seems reasonable to suspect that Descartes meant to emphatically argue the fact that any reasonable person *can* discover himself to be a thinking thing, instead of claiming that we are constantly aware, not only of our thoughts, but also of ourselves as thinking our thoughts.

In *The Evident Connexion* Strawson defends the claim that Descartes' ego cogito is a self-consciousness by quoting the following passage:⁴

'The initial thought by means of which we become aware of something does not differ from the second thought by means of which we become aware that we were aware of it, any more than this second thought differs from the third thought by means of which we become aware that we were aware that we were aware.'⁵

While this, by itself, appears to be convincing proof that Descartes took the ego cogito to be a self-consciousness, it is only because the quote is taken entirely out of context. Descartes intended 'does not differ' to denote a specific and not a numerical identity. It is situated in a broader argument against the idea that thinking could be a property of material substances and Descartes attempts to show that if we allow matter to think, it necessarily follows that matter could also think reflexively, because there is no difference in kind (species) between a thought and a thought directed at a thought.

By proving the existence of the self and its proximity to our thoughts, Descartes has established the means necessary for developing a rationalist epistemology. The truth of a statement is not based on its correspondence with an external reality, but is founded on the well-known principle of clear and distinct ideas.⁶ Of course, to further rid himself of the doubts which occasioned his meditations, he believed it necessary to prove

1 Balibar, *Identity and Difference*, 19.

2 Ibid., 24.

3 Descartes, *Meditations, Objections, and Replies*, 170.

4 Strawson, *The Evident Connexion*, 90.

5 Descartes, *The Philosophical Writings of Descartes*, 2:382.

6 Descartes, *A Discourse on the Method*, 17.

the existence of God and His inability to deceive—matters of little interest to us. I will skip to my objection to Descartes' intuitive self-evidence of the 'I think therefore I am' mentioned at p.13.

§5. *The Intuitive Self-Evidence of the Ego*

Before I get to my objection, we should ask ourselves how we should interpret Descartes' intuitive self-evidence of the 'I think therefore I am'. I'm inclined to take him to mean that we have a direct acquaintance with the I in thinking, that it is immediately given to us—but this is obviously not what Descartes intended. In his reply to Hobbes' second objection, he says:

'But, to explain the matter briefly, it is certainly the case that an act of thinking cannot exist without a thing that thinks, nor in general any act or accident without a substance in which it inheres. However, since we do not immediately know this substance itself through itself, but only through its being a subject of certain acts, it is quite in keeping with the demands of reason and custom for us to call by different names those substances that we recognize to be subjects of obviously different acts or accidents, and afterwards to inquire whether these different names signify one and the same thing.'¹

This indicates that he regarded our knowledge of the self on the same footing as our knowledge of other substantial existences (such as the piece of wax). We are not directly acquainted with it *as a substance* but judge this substance to exist as the subject of the manifold different perceptions, as that which binds them together. Consider also the beginning of paragraph 11 of the *Principles*:

'But now, in order to understand that our mind is not only known earlier and more certainly than the body, but also more clearly; it must be noted that it is very well known by the natural enlightenment which is in our souls that no properties or qualities belong to nothingness; and that accordingly, wherever we perceive some properties or qualities, there we must necessarily find a thing or substance to which they belong; and that the more properties or qualities we perceive in the same thing or substance, the more clearly we know it.'²

Taking into consideration both these passages, I'm led to believe that the intuitive self-evidence consists in the following: When I doubt my own existence, I cannot doubt my doubting. Doubting is perceived to be an act, that is to say, a property, and can therefore not exist apart from the thing whose act it is. The thing which does the doubting, the author of the thought, is the ego. Accordingly, I must necessarily exist

1 Descartes, *Meditations, Objections, and Replies*, 103.

2 Descartes, *Principles of Philosophy*, 6.

because in doubting myself, the doubting presupposes the thing that doubts, which is taken to be myself. I should mention that Descartes took the idea of substance, both corporeal and spiritual, to be innate, not gotten empirically but, as it were, a natural possession of the mind.¹

This argument follows quite logically from the presupposition that thoughts are accidents, but why should we take this to be the case? I admit that *if* they are accidents, then Descartes' argument is sound, but I disagree with the assertion *that* they are. When doubting, the doubt is itself an experience opposite us, it has a certain fullness, a reality. While it might differ from the fullness of spatial objects, it nevertheless does not appear as if contained in the vacuum of an inner subjectivity; I can refer to it substantially as 'that feeling' and as to my knowledge, there is nothing in the concept of this feeling that precludes it from subsisting by itself. There is no difference between the doubting and the doubt. I take this to be true not only of affective or cogitative phenomena (which are often regarded as 'internal'), but also of 'external' phenomena. To quote the largely forgotten W.T. Bush:

'It sounds like an innocent and an intelligible proposition to say that I see the chair on the other side of the room. If, however I mean that an inspection of the situation as experienced reveals any detail of the content that can be called "seeing" as distinct from the visual chair, and other objects in the shape of sensations of head, throat and body, this commonplace statement is false. The situation contains not seeing, but visual and other objects, and if I am interested in the object on the other side of the room in such a way as to make me oblivious of myself, the situation as just then experienced by me contains no seer.'²

Here my argument mirrors that of Lichtenberg: we should not say 'I think' but 'there is thought'.³ We can now reflect Descartes' argument back to him, as it were, by saying that if the thought can be known without knowledge of its subject, then certainly this subject of the thought (i.e., the ego or soul) cannot be essential to the thought. Later interpretations of the cogito, most notably its adaptations by Locke, Berkeley and Hume, reject the distinction between the thought and the object:

'For what are the forementioned objects but the things we perceive by sense, and what do we perceive besides our own ideas or sensations'⁴

'Now we have already observ'd, that however philosophers may distinguish betwixt objects and perception of the senses; which they suppose co-existent and resembling; yet this is a

1 Descartes, *Meditations, Objections, and Replies*, 25; Descartes, *Principles of Philosophy*, 23.

2 Bush, 'An Empirical Definition of Consciousness', 562–63.

3 Lichtenberg, *Schriften Und Briefe*, 2:412.

4 Berkeley, *Principles of Human Knowledge and Three Dialogues between Hylas and Philonous*, 54.

DESCARTES

distinction, which is not comprehended by the generality of mankind, who as they perceive only one being, can never assent to the opinion of a double existence and representation.¹

And it is in this sense that my argument should be understood. If what we denote by phenomenon (or perception) is the same thing which Descartes denotes by the act or accident; then, if we can imagine, without contradicting ourselves, that the phenomenon can subsist on its own, I see no reason to suppose that the doubting of the self, or the perceiving of the wax, should lead us to postulate the existence of a doubter or perceiver.

Admittedly, this argument is complicated by the fact that the perception of the wax is not simply imagined to be a passive awareness of sensations, but that it is only possible through an active and spontaneous apperception, an act of judging the sensations to be sensations of the selfsame wax. I will return to this at a later stage in the text (§17).

¹ Hume, *A Treatise of Human Nature*, 134.

Chapter 2

Locke

§6. Molyneux's Letter

If the problem of personal identity was hidden from Descartes, it was because he equated the self with the *thing that thinks* and assumed the latter to be intuitively self-evident. If it was discovered by Locke, it was only because he rejected the Cartesian ego and had to find another way of explaining wherein the self of a person consists. For him, this self is not 'man' or the substantial soul which inheres in the body, but the result of a continuous consciousness which perceives a multitude of different experiences. The novelty of this theory is easily lost on the many contemporary philosophers already well acquainted with Kantian and phenomenological thought. Thanks to Locke, the relatively obscure topic of personal identity and the concept of consciousness gained a considerable amount of popularity in western philosophy.¹

Locke's account of personal identity is situated in Book II, Chapter XXVII, *Of Identity and Diversity* and was added in the 2nd edition of the *Essay*,² presumably as a result of Molyneux's request for Locke to elaborate on the 'principium individuationis'.³ In this chapter Locke discusses three distinct varieties of identity, each corresponding to a different object: 1. identity of substances; 2. identity of living things, and; 3. identity of persons.⁴ The first section of this chapter (§7) will be dedicated to the first two kinds of identity, why neither of these can account for the identity of person and how Locke's rejection of the Cartesian ego cogito led him to the problem of personal identity. In the second section (§8), I will attempt an empiricist interpretation of consciousness and a refutation of Reid's objection to Locke's theory of personal identity

§7. Discovering the Problem of Personal Identity

Two factors appear to have contributed to Locke's theory of personal identity. First, the diminished importance of substance in Locke's philosophy, and his criticism of the

1 Allison, 'Locke's Theory of Personal Identity', 41.

2 Ibid.

3 Locke, *The Works of John Locke*, 8:310.

4 Locke, *An Essay Concerning Human Understanding*, 298–300.

Cartesian doctrine of the soul as a thinking thing, made it difficult to determine in what the identity of a person consists. Secondly, though not further discussed in this paper, his framing of the question of personal identity in judicial terms—certainly in the latter paragraphs of Chapter XXVII—suggests that Locke did not merely consider the issue of theoretical importance, but also of ethical value.¹ The present section is split into three parts: A. On the identity of substances and living things; B. on the difference between the Lockean and Cartesian ideas of substance, and; C. how both of these factor into the problem of personal identity.

A. THE IDENTITY OF SUBSTANCES AND LIVING THINGS

Locke's *identity of substance* amounts to a strict and metaphysical definition of numerical identity as a thing's being the same with itself qua its being. Two things, however identical in appearance, are not necessarily identical in their existence, if only because they exist in different places at the same time. What grounds these identity statements is not the qualitative resemblances of objects, but their spatio-temporal existence. Locke presupposes that only one thing of a specific substance can occupy any particular place at any particular time.² This makes it so that any substance is the same with itself (as is trivially true) and no two substances can be the same with each other. By substance Locke means God, finite intelligences (spirits) and bodies.³ His argument is most easily understood by focussing on the latter. A body, in its simplest form, is an atom. (This works best if we imagine atoms to be fully indivisible.) According to what was said previously, taken at any moment, such an atom occupies a single determinate place and excludes every other body. From this it follows that one thing can never have two beginnings, nor two things one beginning⁴—the former presupposes one body to have been 'fused' with another body, which is precluded by the fact that every body excludes every other body; the latter presupposes that one body could separate into two, again precluded by the fact that this would suppose the two bodies to have at some point existed at the same place at the same time. Supposedly what Locke had in mind is that we can always trace a single uninterrupted line from any substance as it exists now back to the beginning of its existence.

The identity of a compound object is a simple conjunction of the identities of the single substances which compose it: 'if two or more atoms be joined together into the same mass, every one of those atoms will be the same, by the foregoing rule: while they

1 Strawson, "The Secrets of All Hearts": Locke on Personal Identity'.

2 Locke, *An Essay Concerning Human Understanding*, 296.

3 Ibid.

4 Ibid.

exist united together, the mass, consisting of the same atoms, must be the same mass'.¹ Identity being so defined means that the addition or subtraction of only one atom manages to completely destroy the identity of the whole.

According to Locke, this criterion of spatio-temporal continuity is already enough to answer Molyneux's question: 'tis is easy to discover what is so much inquired after, the *principium individuationis*, and that 'tis plain is existence itself, which determines a being of any sort to a particular time and place incommunicable to two beings of the same kind.² His argument here is rather muddled. It seems to follow that the identities of living beings and persons do not concern *principia individuationis* and are therefore kinds of specific rather than numerical identity. In this case, to be the same man would be to possess a certain property which could theoretically be exhibited by multiple individuals. But this cannot be what Locke is really after. He claims that these different types of identity are the result of our using different ideas:

[B]ut to conceive, and judge of it aright, we must consider what idea the word is applied to, stands for: it being one thing to be the same *substance*, another the same *man*, and a third the same *person*, if *person*, *man*, and *substance*, are three names standing for three different *ideas*; for such as is the idea belonging to that name, such must be the *identity*³

And he at least treats the identity of living beings as if it does individuate objects uniquely.⁴ In contemporary philosophy, we would therefore be inclined to also treat it as a kind of numerical identity.⁵ Locke, on the other hand, equates numerical identity with substance and specific identity with appearance or (relational) properties.

In an empiricist theory of mind, Locke's concept of substantial identity seems somewhat out of place. As we will see in greater detail later (§7.B), Locke does not believe that we can have direct knowledge of substance. We think of it as something—'I know not what'—which is the supposed cause of those things we do perceive.⁶ Though we may very well allow this rigid definition of numerical identity as metaphysical, substantial identity, we should ask ourselves what good such a definition is, if it is entirely outside of the scope of human knowledge.

The *identity of living things* cannot depend on the identity of the underlying substances: Few plants or animals can exist for any extended period of time without exchanging particles with the outside world. If our sole definition of identity were to be a complete correspondence of constitutive parts (atoms), this would mean that no living

1 Locke, *An Essay Concerning Human Understanding*, 298.

2 Ibid., 297.

3 Ibid., 299–300.

4 Ibid., 298.

5 Certainly in the case of living beings, not necessarily in the case of persons.

6 Locke, *An Essay Concerning Human Understanding*, 268.

being could remain identical with itself for any duration whatsoever. Yet, in everyday life we can easily distinguish one tree from another and know that our cat today is the same cat it was a few years ago, though the atoms which make up her body have changed considerably. To account for this new form of identity, some other condition is needed: *organisation*.

'We must therefore consider wherein an oak differs from a mass of matter, and that seems to me to be in this; that the one is only the cohesion of particles anyhow united, the other such a disposition of them as constitutes the parts of an oak [...] That being then one plant, which has such an organization of parts in one coherent body, partaking of one common life, it continues to be the same plant, as long as it partakes of the same life, though that life be communicated to new particles of matter vitally united to the living plant, in a like continued fashion, conformable to that sort of plant.'¹

A rock, when it loses some of its constitutive particles, is not the same rock any more; whereas an oak, or any living being, as long as it lives, remains the same being no matter how many of its atoms have been replaced. It is also in this that the bodily identity of humans consists. A woman is the same woman as long as there is a continued organisation of life which particles partake in. The distinction between substances and living things allows us to distinguish our identities as immaterial spirits from our identities as human beings.

B. LOCKE'S CONCEPT OF SUBSTANCE

Contrary to Descartes, Locke does not believe that we have an innate idea of substance. If we have any idea of it at all, it is a confused one, we think of it as 'an uncertain supposition of we know not what (*i.e.* of something whereof we have no particular distinct positive) idea, which we take to be the *substratum*, or support, of those ideas, we do know.'² Or as he puts it elsewhere: 'So that of *substance*, we have no idea of what it is, but only a confused obscure one of what it does.'³ It follows that when we speak of a substance, we merely intend a certain unknown X which has the power⁴ to produce all kinds of ideas in us and interact with other objects, e.g., the ability of lapis lazuli to cause the sensation of blue, as well as to be powdered and suspended in oil for use as a paint. This is true of both body and spirit.

Our knowledge of reality is based on experience which, by sensation or reflection,

¹ Locke, *An Essay Concerning Human Understanding*, 298.

² *Ibid.*, 100.

³ *Ibid.*, 169.

⁴ 'Powers therefore justly make a great part of our complex ideas of substances.' *Ibid.*, 272.

furnishes us with ideas.¹ Locke's concept of ideas seems to be derived from Descartes' concept of thoughts and certainly matches it in breadth; but whereas Descartes' concept denotes modes of thought which are necessarily dependent on a substantial mind, Locke's 'ideas' refer to thoughts and things alike as independent entities. When we experience the red of a flower, we do not thereby have a positive idea of the flower as a substantial something in which the red inheres or of the existence of any substance whatsoever. Similarly, when we feel happy at the sight of a friend, we do not thereby know what it is that feels happy, whether it is a soul or body or nothing outside of experience at all.

Despite this, Locke himself continues to believe in the existence of substances, both bodies and spirits. He merely denies that experience affords us any knowledge of them. Like Descartes, he associates spirit with the ideas of thinking and will,² but his own philosophy prevents him from saying that it is the essence of spirit to be a thinking thing. A main criticism of Locke is that we cannot possibly know the soul to be constantly thinking and it is rather absurd to assume so without evidence:

'I confess myself to have one of those dull souls, that doth not perceive itself always to contemplate ideas; nor can conceive it any more necessary for the *soul always to think*, than for the body always to move; the perception of ideas being (as I conceive) to the soul, what motion is to the body, not its essence, but one of its operations'³

It is strange to say that a man, while dreamlessly sleeping, thinks. Thinking refers to a positive idea in our minds and, as such, an unconscious or unaware thinking is a contradiction in terms; it being impossible to experience, and consequently to know, unconscious thought: 'They [Cartesians] who talk thus, may, with as much reason, if it be necessary to their hypothesis, say, that a man is always hungry, but that he does not always feel it: whereas hunger consists in that very sensation, as thinking consists in being conscious that one thinks.'⁴ He concludes his argument rather humorously by saying:

'But it is but defining the soul to be "a substance that always thinks," and the business is done. If such definition be of any authority, I know not what it can serve for but to make many men suspect that they have no souls at all; since they find a good part of their lives pass away without thinking.'⁵

1 Locke, *An Essay Concerning Human Understanding*, 109.

2 *Ibid.*, 277.

3 *Ibid.*, 112.

4 *Ibid.*, 118.

5 *Ibid.*, 119.

C. THE PROBLEM OF PERSONAL IDENTITY

Locke is now faced with a problem: The identity of a person cannot be equated with the identity of an immaterial substance because, if it is admitted that the soul may think while I'm unaware of it, these thoughts can hardly be attributed to me. Neither, for that matter, can it be equated with the identity of a living being. During dreamless sleep, though my bodily processes continue throughout the night, I myself awake immediately after falling asleep without a break or disruption in my awareness. The problem of personal identity can be expressed as follows: 'How can the unity of a person be explained immanently, without reference to anything outside of, or underlying, thought?' This is complicated by the fact that thoughts are not by themselves given as interconnected. For Locke, thoughts are to the soul what motion is to the body:

'[O]nly as to things whose existence is in succession, such as are the actions of finite beings, *v.g. motion* and *thought*, both which consist in a continued train of succession, concerning their diversity there can be no question: because each perishing the moment it begins, they cannot exist in different times, or in different places, as permanent beings can at different times exist in distant places; and therefore no motion or thought, considered as at different times, can be the same, each part thereof having a different beginning of existence.'

¹

They're a form of succession, each different from the other. In his chapters on duration, Locke defines an *instant* (or moment) as '*that which takes up the time of only one idea in our minds*'² and *time* as the apparent distance between different moments.³ Because of this, each thought necessarily 'perishes the moment it begins'. The problem of personal identity should be understood as a result of his criticism of the Cartesian theory of the substantial self and consequently the difference in reference between the soul and the self. Whereas, in Cartesian philosophy, the existence of thought coincides with the existence of the soul, as also, the existence of the soul coincides with that of thought; in Lockean philosophy this equality is lost. The solution to the problem of personal identity is, rather famously, a reliance on consciousness and memory.

§8. *Of Identity and Diversity*

'For since consciousness always accompanies thinking, and 'tis that that makes everyone to be what he calls *self*; and thereby distinguishes himself from all other thinkings things; in this alone consists *personal identity*, *i.e.* the sameness of a rational being: and as far as this

1 Locke, *An Essay Concerning Human Understanding*, 297.

2 *Ibid.*, 177.

3 *Ibid.*, 179–81.

consciousness can be extended backwards to any past action or thought, so far reaches the identity of that *person*¹

'For as far as any intelligent being can repeat the idea of any past action with the same consciousness it had of it at first, and with the same consciousness it has of any present action; so far is it the same *personal self*.'²

Interpreting the relationship between self, consciousness and memory in the *Essay* is difficult. For one, Locke's definition of consciousness does not make it immediately clear how it relates all the different and separate thoughts to one person. For another, there is little consensus on Locke's original intention so a 'canonical' reading of the chapter is practically impossible. While I do endeavour, by the end of this section, to show wherein personal identity might consist, I do not wish to attribute the entirety of the following arguments to Locke himself.

I will argue that, contrary to popular belief,³ Locke did not advocate a simple memory theory of personal identity and will instead propose an alternative interpretation of the connection between memory, consciousness and the self which, I hope the reader will agree, does not presuppose anything outside of the original text and appears in line with the empiricist aim of Locke's work. I wish to show the following: that consciousness should not be regarded as a thing present in a multitude of distinct and separate experiences, nor memory as intrinsically more important to personal identity than other perceptions, but that consciousness is, by its very definition, experientially continuous. I will rely primarily on Locke's definitions of consciousness in Chapters I and XXVII of Book II, and his definition of memory in Chapter X.

The idea that Locke's theory of personal identity is not a simple memory theory,⁴ or at least needn't be,⁵ is not itself new; but the popularity of the opposing view means that it at least warrants a defence. The simple memory theory states that 'I am the same person as someone in the past, just in case I remember having an experience as that person.'⁶ It establishes a numerical identity of person on the basis of remembrance. If person A has a memory of person B, then A and B are one and the same person. This theory has the benefit of being easily intelligible: I know that I am the same person I was in high school because I remember the awkwardness of adolescence. The downside

1 Locke, *An Essay Concerning Human Understanding*, 302.

2 *Ibid.*, 303.

3 Hongladarom, 'Personal Identity and the Self in the Online and Offline World', 538–39; Reid, *Essays on the Intellectual Powers of Man*, 1:395–401; Allison, 'Locke's Theory of Personal Identity'.

4 Yaffe, 'Locke on Consciousness, Personal Identity and the Idea of Duration'.

5 Klein and Nichols, 'Memory and the Sense of Personal Identity', 691.

6 *Ibid.*, 690.

of this intelligibility is that it is accompanied by many paradoxes and contradictions. One of these is Thomas Reid's paradox of the brave officer:

'Suppose a brave officer to have been flogged when a boy at school, for robbing an orchard, to have taken a standard from the enemy in his first campaign, and to have been made a general in advanced life: Suppose also, which must be admitted to be possible, that when he took the standard, he was conscious of his having been flogged at school, and that when made a general he was conscious of his taking the standard, but had absolutely lost the consciousness of his flogging.'¹

The argument goes: if person *B* at t_2 recognizes himself to be the same as person *A* at t_1 , then person *C* at t_3 who is the same person as *B* must necessarily be the same as person *A*. In Locke's theory, however, it is possible for *C* not to remember the occurrences at t_1 because of which he is not the same as *A*, even though he is the same as *B* who is the same as *A*.

To show that Locke's theory of personal identity is not a simple memory theory, and consequently that Reid's paradox is not applicable to Locke, I will argue two points: First and most importantly, that personal identity does not consist solely in memory. Secondly, that, since the relation between person *A* and *B* is secondary to consciousness, it is not a simple expression of logical or numerical identity and does not imply transitivity.

The first point, that personal identity consists in more than memory alone, should be easy to prove. After all, Locke outright tells us that the body is also part of ourselves:

'That this is so, we have some kind of evidence in our very bodies, all whose particles, whilst vitally united to this same thinking conscious self, so that we feel when they are touched, and are affected by, and conscious of good or harm that happens to them, are a part of *ourselves*; *i.e.* of our thinking conscious *self*. Thus, the limbs of his body are to everyone a part of *himself*; he sympathizes and is concerned for them.'²

And later on:

'Thus everyone finds, that whilst comprehended under that consciousness, the little finger is as much a part of *itself*, as what is most so.'³

As to the second point: the idea that personal identity should be transitive cannot be attributed to Locke and is mostly the result of Reid's faulty interpretation of Locke's concepts of 1. consciousness and 2. memory.

1 Reid, *Essays on the Intellectual Powers of Man*, 1:397.

2 Locke, *An Essay Concerning Human Understanding*, 303.

3 *Ibid.*, 307.

1. Though Reid is quick to equate consciousness with memory or ‘distinct remembrance’,¹ Locke’s concept of consciousness bears no necessary connection to memory. It is first defined as ‘the perception of what passes in a man’s own mind.’² A definition that, though sometimes differently worded, is consistently maintained throughout the *Essay*. E.g., in Chapter XXVII, *On Identity and Diversity*: ‘that consciousness, which is inseparable from thinking, and as it seems to me essential to it: it being impossible for any one to perceive, without perceiving that he does perceive.’³ This ‘perceiving that he does perceive’ should not be taken to mean that we are at every moment intimately aware of our own awareness. In light of Locke’s critique of Cartesian philosophy, he can be best understood as saying that the thinking of the substantial soul cannot be regarded as the same thing as the thinking of the person—what he denotes by perceiving to perceive is no different from perceiving simpliciter, it merely serves to distinguish our positive idea of perception from the Cartesian soul which can think (perceive) without being aware of its thoughts.

Locke’s concept of consciousness therefore corresponds to what we ordinarily call experience: To be conscious of a memory as my memory is simply to remember; to be conscious of a bodily sensation as my sensation is simply to feel it. When I stub my toe, I experience pain radiating outwards from a bodily location, and this is all that is required to relate this pain to myself. Whether this pain is justified or not (e.g., in the case of phantom pain), or whether what I remember actually happened or not, does not matter. A mistaken memory can bring me just as much pride or embarrassment as a true one.

Despite wrongfully equating consciousness with distinct remembrance, Reid did correctly understand that Locke’s concept of consciousness was not one of a continued and numerically identical consciousness throughout the multitude of temporally distinct experiences, but always of a discrete and separate consciousness.⁴ My consciousness at t_1 is different from that at t_2 which is again different from my consciousness at t_3 . It is not a persistent thing or act which reaches beyond each particular thought, but is at every moment defined anew by the contents of my (possible) awareness.

‘I grant, were the same consciousness the same individual action, it could not: but it being but a present representation of a past action, why it may not be possible, that that may be represented to the mind to have been, which really never was, remains to be shown.’⁵

1 Reid, *Essays on the Intellectual Powers of Man*, 1:398.

2 Locke, *An Essay Concerning Human Understanding*, 118.

3 *Ibid.*, 302.

4 Reid, *Essays on the Intellectual Powers of Man*, 1:401.

5 Locke, *An Essay Concerning Human Understanding*, 304.

2. As to Locke's concept of memory: though he talks of memory as if it's a storehouse filled with past ideas, he makes it clear that this is meant as an analogy and not as a matter of fact:

'But our ideas being nothing, but actual perceptions in the mind, which cease to be anything, when there is no perception of them, this *laying up* of our ideas in the repository of the memory, signifies no more but this, that the mind has a power, in many cases, to revive perceptions, which it has once had, with this additional perception annexed to them, that it has had them before. And in this sense it is, that our ideas are said to be in our memories, when indeed they are actually nowhere, but only there is an ability in the mind, when it will, to revive them again'¹

Though in this passage he refers to the perceptions of memory as 'past perceptions', which seemingly implies that memories must necessarily refer to experiences which actually took place, and which would preclude false memories; in Chapter XXVII he admits that false memories are possible² and allowing some interpretative liberty we can then define Locke's concept in a strictly positive, empirical fashion as a perception accompanied by the perception of it having occurred in the past.

Keeping these facts in mind, we can already refute Reid's paradox. If what is presented in memory is not necessarily related to an actual happening, but is merely a 'present representation of a past action',³ or rather, a present representation of what is experienced to be a past action, then any relation of personal identity which is based on the consciousness of this memory, is not a connection between two factual beings—person A existing at t_1 and person B existing at t_2 —but merely between my present self and what I remember experiencing as if in the past. More important still, because my consciousness at t_2 , which is the basis for my affirmation that person B is the same as person A, is not the same as my consciousness at t_3 , which is my basis for affirming that person C is the same as B but not A, there is no contradiction to speak of. To better show why this is not necessary, let me rephrase Reid's paradox but replace B's memory of A with the bodily experience of his arm, and assume that between t_2 and t_3 his arm was amputated. In this case, we do not find it paradoxical that person B, whose self contains the experience of his arm, and person C, who no longer has this experience, can be one and the same person; even though the person would both need to have and not have an arm, as in Reid's paradox, he would both be and not be person A. We might even assume that when C remembers B, he does not particularly remember how it felt to have his arm—if, for example, it was amputated a very long time ago—as in Reid's case C did not remember A. The reason why there is no contradiction in either of these

¹ Locke, *An Essay Concerning Human Understanding*, 147–48.

² *Ibid.*, 304.

³ *Ibid.*

cases is because it is not in relation to the same consciousness that *A* is affirmed to be *B* and *C* is affirmed to be *B* but not *A*.

A third problem underlying Reid's interpretation of Locke is his understanding of time and duration with regard to continuous existence. For something to be identical to itself at different points in time, it must continuously exist. This is most apparent in Reid's final remarks:

'As our consciousness sometimes ceases to exist, as in sound sleep, our personal identity must cease with it. Mr. LOCKE allows, that the same thing cannot have two beginnings of existence, so that our identity would be irrecoverably gone every time we cease to think, if it was but for a moment.'¹

Admittedly, quite a few of Locke's statements seem to confirm Reid's idea of interruptions in consciousness, e.g., 'I say, in all these cases, our consciousness being interrupted, and we losing the sight of our past selves [...]'.² And Locke does appear to regard at least temporal continuity as a requirement for personal identity: 'In all which account of *self*, the same numerical substance is not considered as making the same *self*: but the same continued consciousness'.³ I will argue, however, that the interruptions, which are remarked on both by Locke and Reid, are compatible with the continuity of existence presupposed by both, given Locke's theory of duration and his assertion that the 'same consciousness' does not denote 'the same action' but is always a numerically different act of consciousness. I cannot confidently claim that this reply to Reid's objection would coincide with Locke's, but I believe that it might and even if it doesn't, manages to solve the problem quite well. On my interpretation, Locke's identity of person is a kind of specific identity; both in the Lockean sense, as not being a substantial identity, and in the contemporary sense, as not necessarily individuating an object uniquely.

There's some textual support for my claim that Locke's theory of personal identity is connected to his theory of duration:

'For whilst we are thinking, or whilst we receive successively several ideas in our minds, we know that we do exist; and so we call the existence, or the continuation of the existence of ourselves, or anything else, commensurate to the succession of any ideas in our minds, the *duration* of ourselves, or any such other thing co-existent with our thinking.'⁴

Central to Locke's theory of duration (Chapter XIV) is its reliance on thought. *Dura-*

- 1 Reid, *Essays on the Intellectual Powers of Man*, 1:401.
- 2 Locke, *An Essay Concerning Human Understanding*, 303.
- 3 *Ibid.*, 311.
- 4 *Ibid.*, 175.

tion, he claims, consists in the succession of ideas in the mind. For example: in sleeping ‘whether an hour, or a day, a month, or a year; of which duration of things, whilst he sleeps, or thinks not, he has no perception at all’;¹ consider also the opposite case: when ideas are rushing through our mind, an equal time period can appear considerably longer. What Locke denotes by duration could arguably be called a subjective experience of time, which is our primary and original way of experiencing it. Objective time, or simply called *time*,² is only gotten by virtue of inferences. It is the measured time of, e.g., the solar cycle and the 24-hour clock. To use the sun as an example: perceiving the interval between each sunrise to be apparently equal in duration, we simply *assume* that these stretches of time really are equal and use them to divide and measure the passing of time. In this way, we arrive at two different concepts: one subjective and based on the succession of ideas: *duration*; the other objective, based on the assumed equal duration between certain perceptions: *time*. The latter appears to be the only sense of time thought of by Reid, and the one Locke had in mind when referring to the interruptions in consciousness. But as there are two concepts of time, and identity is thought relative to time by virtue of its reliance on the continued existence of a thing, it is entirely possible, and I think likely, that Locke meant the former concept of time, i.e., duration, to be relevant in his discussion of the personal identity. Because, though consciousness may be interrupted in objective time (which, as noted above, is inferential), it never is in subjective time. Take Locke’s example of Adam and Eve:

‘But if Adam and Eve (when they were alone in the world) instead of their ordinary night’s sleep, had passed the whole 24 hours in one continued sleep, the duration of that 24 hours had been irrecoverably lost to them, and been forever left out of their account of time.’³

Our idea of objective time is largely based on empirical factors, e.g., the sun, moon, seasons. If it came to be that someone, separated from the rest of mankind, spent an entire day sleeping, only to awaken the next day seeing the sun rise as usual, he would have no idea that he’d lost a day. When the passing of ideas ceases, we do not experience the duration of our unconsciousness, instead we experience our return to consciousness as immediately succeeding our last idea. Without an empirical sign of our absence, a change in lighting, in the position of objects or the feeling of our body, we would not know that any duration had passed at all—‘the moment he leaves off to think, till the moment he begins to think again, seems to him to have no distance.’⁴ Time in this sense, subjective time, duration, is co-existent with thought and, as is my

1 Locke, *An Essay Concerning Human Understanding*, 175.

2 Ibid., 179.

3 Ibid., 176.

4 Ibid., 175.

argument, consciousness. To better illustrate the difference between duration and time, we can graph the relation between both (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Locke: Relation Duration-Time

We can see that the experience of duration (y-axis) is continuous, whereas that of time (x-axis) can be interrupted. By regarding the continuity of consciousness as relative to duration rather than time, Locke's argument ceases to be one of synthetic self-recognition, but becomes one of analytic necessity. When any moment is lost, when it leaves the scope of experience, whatever preceded and succeeded it join together and the break between both is smoothed over.

Seeing as how it is not the same act of consciousness throughout, but rather a separate act each moment, and memory is nothing but perception with the idea of 'having been' attached to it, my past experience is only part of my self because it is actually a present experience, or as Locke puts it: 'a present representation of a past action'.¹ It is part of myself in the same way that my bodily sensations are part of myself; they are presently 'perceived to be perceived'—I'm presently conscious of them.

Since I am not conscious of interruptions in duration and the concept of objective time is purely inferential, that I forget or sleep might count as an interruption in objective time, but it is not one in duration or subjective time. Each memory follows the other as if in a continuous flow of ideas, the only mark of an interruption is our empirical knowledge that, e.g., in reality I cannot instantaneously go from the train station to my home, while in memory I can perceive myself on a train at one moment and at home the next, without any interval in between. If, as in the case of Adam and Eve, we

¹ Locke, *An Essay Concerning Human Understanding*, 304.

had no reason to suspect an interruption, even though we actually did forget something, or were unconscious, we wouldn't experience a blank in memory at all.

We can regard personal identity as the result of this gapless consciousness of ideas in the mind. This explains why, though I may at some point in time forget all my past memories, I will still be self to myself, though arguably, regarded over time, a different self. I cannot prove that this is the correct interpretation, though I hope I'm not mistaken in thinking that it is a good interpretation, one that presupposes little outside the original text and serves to understand many of its complexities quite well. And, having discovered the simple memory theory to be clearly insufficient, I hope the reader will also understand the need for this largely exegetical section.

It may be asked to what extent Locke has actually succeeded in distancing himself from Descartes. Certainly, he does not equate the self with the soul, but by taking our empirical and positive idea of time to be that of duration, i.e., the succession of thoughts in the mind, it would seem as if the self is once again a 'thing that always thinks'—this is the conclusion arrived at by Berkeley, starting from the same premisses.

Time therefore being nothing, abstracted from the succession of ideas in our minds, it follows that the duration of any finite spirit must be estimated by the number of ideas or actions succeeding each other in the same spirit or mind. Hence it is a plain consequence that the soul always thinks: and in truth whoever shall go about to divide in his thought, or abstract the *existence* of a spirit from its *cogitation*, will, I believe, find it no easy task.¹

¹ Berkeley, *Principles of Human Knowledge and Three Dialogues between Hylas and Philonous*, 89.

Chapter 3

Hume

The present chapter is divided into five sections: First (§9), an introductory section on the distinction between real and fictitious ideas in Humean philosophy. Secondly (§10), an interpretation of Section 1.4.6's organic theory of personal identity. Thirdly (§11), critical considerations concerning this theory based on Penelhum's objection in *Hume on Personal Identity*. Fourthly (§12), a brief discussion of the infamous self-professed 'inconsistency' in Hume's theory of personal identity mentioned in the *Appendix* to the *Treatise*. And fifthly (§13), an objection to a constructive, causal realist idea of mind as proposed by Strawson in his interpretation of the problem of the *Appendix*.

§9. *Real and Fictitious Ideas*

According to Hume, the self or person is a fiction and the problem of personal identity consists in figuring out how this particular fiction can arise. The purpose of this introductory section is to acquaint the reader with Hume's distinction between real and fictitious ideas; that is: 1.a to show how real ideas come about, 1.b what they are, as well as 2.a how fictions come about and 2.b how we should conceive of them.

1.a The origin of philosophical, empirical or real ideas is described by Hume in the first section of *Treatise, Of the origin of our ideas* (1.1.1), concerning his empiricist theory of perception. As is well known, he distinguishes two kinds of perceptions: *impressions* and *ideas*. These should not be interpreted as ontological categories, they principally can't be, Hume's anti-dogmatic standpoint precludes him from discussing the 'true nature' of things. Instead, the distinction is marked by qualitative differences in the perceptions themselves.

'Thus in sleep, in a fever, in madness, or in any very violent emotions of soul, our ideas may approach to our impressions: As on the other hand it sometimes happens, that our impressions are so faint and low, that we cannot distinguish them from our ideas.'¹

Impressions, which is a generic name for *sensations, passions and emotions*,² are distin-

¹ Hume, *A Treatise of Human Nature*, 7.

² *Ibid.*

guished from *ideas* by the superior 'force and liveliness, with which they strike upon the mind'.¹ *Ideas* are the 'faint images of these [impressions] in thinking and reasoning'.²

One regular connection holds between them: there can never be an idea without an antecedent impression. 'We cannot form to ourselves a just idea of the taste of a pineapple, without having actually tasted it.'³ This relation of antecedence is an empirical and apparent relation, not one that objectively exists, it being a well-known principle in Hume's philosophy that we can have no knowledge of real causation.

Besides the distinction between impressions and ideas, perceptions can also be distinguished into *simple* and *complex*. *Simple* perceptions are 'such as admit of no distinction nor separation',⁴ *complex* perceptions are those which 'may be distinguish'd into parts'.⁵ The perception of a chair, for example, is *complex* because I can easily distinguish the seat from the legs and the back, and can further distinguish different colours and tactile parts in each of these. As to *simple* ideas, they are the smallest quanta of our perceptions: the perceptual dots of colour, the smallest distinguishable units of tactile sensation, the specific and singular tastes and smells. All complex impressions and ideas resolve themselves into simple perceptions and are really only the latter united in a particular way.

A maxim regarding these perceptions, which is reiterated throughout the *Treatise* and summarised in the *Appendix*, reads:

'Whatever is distinct, is distinguishable; and whatever is distinguishable, is separable by the thought or imagination. All perceptions are distinct. They are, therefore, distinguishable, and separable, and may be conceiv'd as separately existent, and may exist separately, without any contradiction or absurdity.'⁶

For Hume, this maxim marks the limits of our real ideas: we can only know what we perceive and if the multitude singular perceptions which constitute an experience can be thought separate from each other, then they can be thought to exist separately, and we cannot claim them to be truly united. Our knowledge of their unity, e.g., of the multitude sensible points which make up my perception of a chair, cannot be a real unity, that is to say: we cannot have a positive idea of it because deep down we have no clue as to what binds them together.

We can think back to Descartes' piece of wax (p.14), his argument resembles that of Hume. Like Descartes, Hume claims that there is a lot less given to the senses than we

1 Hume, *A Treatise of Human Nature*, 7.

2 Ibid.

3 Ibid., 9. A popular example, see: Locke, *An Essay Concerning Human Understanding*, 558.

4 Hume, *A Treatise of Human Nature*, 7.

5 Ibid.

6 Ibid., 399.

generally assume. Since everything that is separable is distinguishable, and can be thought to exist by itself, and every simple perception can certainly be thought separate from every other perception, there is no apparent reason why the multitude of different simple perceptions which constitute a chair should be regarded as parts of a larger whole. Remember also Locke's rejection of the positive idea of substance (p. 24), which precludes Hume from saying, as Descartes did, that we simply judge the different qualities to inhere in the same unchanging something. If we have an idea of substance, this idea must be derived from an impression, but as—resembling Descartes' example—this is exactly what is being denied, all we're left with is a collection of different sensations. As a result, we can have no positive idea of substance whatsoever. Echoing Locke, Hume argues that substance is an 'unknown *something*' in which the particular qualities are supposed to inhere, it is a 'fiction'.¹ While, in examining our experience, we find only separable and distinguishable perceptions, separate existences; our mind naturally supposes something more.

1.b If we attempt to define what it means to be a 'real idea', we can say that it is an idea which 'represent[s] the objects or impressions, from which [it is] deriv'd'.²

But aren't all ideas derived from impressions? If we are to believe Hume,³ they certainly are. But as is often remarked upon, and at a later time lamented by Hume himself,⁴ he is not very careful in how he expresses himself. We know for a fact that he believes in the existence of other ideas, e.g., the self, causation, geometric figures, which are not properly empirical, which cannot be derived from impressions, but which are nonetheless ideas. What he should have said is that all our *positive* ideas are derived from impressions. It is certainly possible to have other ideas, but these are the result of the imagination and have no real 'content', they do not 'represent' anything.

2.a The imagination is the faculty of the mind responsible for transposing and changing, separating and joining ideas.⁵ Guiding its natural operations are three principles of association: *resemblance*, *contiguity* and *causation*.⁶ These principles of association, or the connection of ideas, are to be regarded as a 'gentle force'⁷ which inclines us to think of different ideas as connected where we cannot truthfully perceive any such connection. For example, the perception of red easily introduces the idea of blood to our mind (resemblance); the perception of a river that of fish (contiguity,) and; the perception of fire that of heat (causation).

1 Hume, *A Treatise of Human Nature*, 16.

2 Ibid., 30.

3 Ibid., 9.

4 Burton, *Life and Correspondence of David Hume*, 98.

5 Hume, *A Treatise of Human Nature*, 12.

6 Ibid., 13.

7 Ibid., 12.

'Here is a kind of ATTRACTION, which in the mental world will be found to have as extraordinary effects as in the natural, and to show itself in as many and as various forms. Its effects are every where conspicuous; but as to its causes, they are mostly unknown, and must be resolv'd into *original* qualities of human nature, which I pretend not to explain.'¹

These are all the principles necessary to explain how fictitious ideas occur and, as a matter of fact, causation is itself a fictitious relation that comes about by a regular (resemblance) conjunction of two objects wherein one temporally precedes the other (contiguity).

2.b A fictitious idea is any idea which is not derived from an antecedent impression, but is instead the result of the functioning of the imagination, viz. the principles of resemblance, contiguity and causation. In the present case we're only interested in *natural* fictions, fictitious ideas which occur by a psychological tendency of the human mind, as opposed to *artificial* fictions, such as artistic creations, which are the result of a conscious effort.

§10. *The Organic Fiction*

Section 1.4.6 of the *Treatise* deals with the topic of personal identity. It is part of a broader discussion on identity starting at Section 1.4.2, and like the identity of objects discussed in the preceding sections (1.4.2–4), Hume takes personal identity to be a fiction: It is a thing which we, by a natural tendency of the imagination, believe in, despite lacking any empirical basis. In relation to Sections 1.4.2–6, it should be mentioned that the problem of identity, both personal and objective, is not one of *justification* or *real existence*, but of *how the fiction of identity is possible*.

'We may well ask, *What causes induce us to believe in the existence of body?* But 'tis in vain to ask, *Whether there be body or not?*'²

Justification and real existence are of little interest because Hume is not concerned with *whether* numerical identity may be attributed to an object or the self—it may not—but *why* we attribute it regardless. Numerical identity is defined as 'the *invariableness* and *uninterruptedness* of any object, thro' a suppos'd variation of time'.³ This naturally excludes talk of identity with regard to changing objects. The fact that we *do* attribute identity to such objects, often with great practical value and few problems, requires an explanation.

1 Hume, *A Treatise of Human Nature*, 14.

2 Ibid., 125.

3 Ibid., 134.

The principal targets of these sections are the ‘ancient’ and ‘modern’ philosophers who, rather than accepting the fact that we cannot discover any trace of true identity in these perceptions, attempt to justify our purely psychological inclination to regard them as identical by postulating the existence of substances or primary qualities. Instead of resting content with what we do know, they theorise that there is some meta-physical relation, real but hidden, which accounts for our behaviour.¹

Now it’s certainly true that the idea of person cannot consist in the ‘invariableness’ and ‘uninterruptedness’ of numerical identity. There’s nothing in our manifold perceptions which, from the moment we are born until the moment we die, stays exactly the same.

‘But there is no impression constant and invariable. Pain and pleasure, grief and joy, passions and sensations succeed each other, and never all exist at the same time.’²

The only thing we discover is a succession of unrelated ideas and impressions:

‘[W]hen I enter most intimately into what I call *myself*, I always stumble on some particular perception or other, of heat or cold, light or shade, love or hatred, pain or pleasure.’³

‘I may venture to affirm of the rest of mankind, that they are nothing but a bundle or collection of different perceptions, which succeed each other with an inconceivable rapidity, and are in a perpetual flux and movement. Our eyes cannot turn in their sockets without varying our perceptions. Our thought is still more variable than our sight; and all our other senses and faculties contribute to this change; nor is there any single power of the soul, which remains unalterably the same, perhaps for one moment.’⁴

This last passage has led some philosophers to characterise Hume as a bundle-theorist; a view rejected by most, if not all, Hume interpreters.⁵ Instead, what he proposes is an organic, systemic view of personal identity.⁶ The ‘bundle’ is meant in a negative sense, to express that ‘human beings are not composed of something called a “self” *plus* some other, less permanent, items, but only of these latter items themselves.’⁷ Because of this, there’s no clear-cut distinction between personal and non-personal identity

1 Hume, *A Treatise of Human Nature*, 144–52.

2 Ibid., 164.

3 Ibid., 165.

4 Ibid.

5 Strawson, *The Evident Connexion*, 73; Brett, ‘Substance and Mental Identity in Hume’s Treatise’, 111; Mendus, ‘Personal Identity: The Two Analogies in Hume’.

6 Brett, ‘Substance and Mental Identity in Hume’s Treatise’, 111; Mendus, ‘Personal Identity: The Two Analogies in Hume’.

7 Penelhum, ‘Hume on Personal Identity’, 574.

(something I will argue for myself in §22);¹ we have no privileged way of knowing ourselves, are not born with insight into the behind-the-scenes of our subjective experiences. Like the identity of objects, the self cannot be equated with this aggregate of perceptions, but is constituted by associative connections.

His solution to the problem of identity in changing objects (and subjects) relies on the psychological assumption that the actions of the imagination in perceiving a numerically identical object subjectively resemble the actions in perceiving a multitude of closely related objects:

‘But tho’ these two ideas of identity, and a succession of related objects be in themselves perfectly distinct, and even contrary, yet ’tis certain, that in our common way of thinking they are generally confounded with each other. That action of the imagination, by which we consider the uninterrupted and invariable object, and that by which we reflect on the succession of related objects, are almost the same feeling, nor is there much more effort requir’d in the latter than in the former.’²

According to Hume, the two most important relations in explaining the attribution of identity are resemblance and causation. The first is the relation principally responsible for establishing objective identity:³

‘We find by experience, that there is such a *constancy* in almost all the impressions of the senses, that their interruption produces no alteration on them, and hinders them not from returning the same in appearance and in situation as at their first existence.’⁴

And its role in personal identity is mostly linked to repeated remembrance:

‘[M]ust not the frequent placing of these resembling perceptions in the chain of thought, convey the imagination more easily from one link to another, and make the whole seem like the continuance of one object?’⁵

But this alone cannot sufficiently explain personal identity, as even a sudden and significant change in the content of my perceptions will not disturb my relation to my past self. This is where causation comes in. Like Mendus,⁶ I will explain the role of causation in Hume’s theory of personal identity by focussing on the two main analo-

1 Mendus, ‘Personal Identity: The Two Analogies in Hume’, 63.

2 Hume, *A Treatise of Human Nature*, 165–66.

3 Ibid., 135.

4 Ibid., 136.

5 Ibid., 170.

6 Mendus, ‘Personal Identity: The Two Analogies in Hume’.

gies in Section 1.4.6: the analogy of animals and plants and the analogy of the commonwealth. Both of these depend on two special relations of causation.

On the one hand, causation with regard to a *common end* or *purpose*:

‘There is, however, another artifice, by which we may induce the imagination to advance a step farther; and that is by producing a reference of the parts to each other, and a combination to some *common end* or *purpose*.’¹

This is the case when, e.g., despite frequent reparations, we continue to regard a ship as the same ship though many of its parts have been replaced²—an example given by Hume, presumably in reference to the ship of Theseus. Such a common end is also present in animals and plants, where all organs contribute to the continuation of the whole; and commonwealths, where each individual (supposedly) acts in accordance with the common good. As noted by Mendus³ and Brett,⁴ our ascription of identity can be extremely arbitrary. If we pushed Hume for an answer concerning ‘Theseus’ paradox, it is more than likely that he would say that we ‘may as well make up whatever answer [we feel] satisfied with.’⁵ Again: Hume is not concerned with whether we should ascribe identity to an object, but *why* we do.

On the other hand, both analogies presuppose a *sympathy* between the parts of the object:

‘[W]hen we add a *sympathy* of parts to their *common end*, and suppose that they bear to each other, the reciprocal relation of cause and effect in all their actions and operations. The effect [...] is, that tho’ every one must allow, that in a very few years both vegetables and animals endure a *total* change, yet we still attribute identity to them’⁶

Hume’s idea of sympathy resembles Locke’s concept of organisation (p.24), though applied to a broader range of objects. By and large, in the human organism, every organ is simultaneously the cause and end of every other organ. The same goes for the commonwealth:

‘Our impressions give rise to their correspondent ideas; and these ideas in their turn produce other impressions. One thought chases another, and draws after it a third, by which it is expell’d in its turn. In this respect, I cannot compare the soul more properly to any thing than to a republic or commonwealth, in which the several members are so united by the reciprocal

1 Hume, *A Treatise of Human Nature*, 168.

2 Ibid.

3 Mendus, ‘Personal Identity: The Two Analogies in Hume’, 65.

4 Brett, ‘Substance and Mental Identity in Hume’s Treatise’, 118.

5 Ibid.

6 Hume, *A Treatise of Human Nature*, 168.

ties of government and subordination, and give rise to other persons, who propagate the same republic in the incessant changes of its part.¹

The value of these analogies in explaining personal identity, are the similarities between the self, living beings and human societies:

'We now proceed to explain the nature of *personal identity* [...] And here 'tis evident, the same method of reasoning must be continu'd, which has so successfully explain'd the identity of plants, and animals, and ships, and houses [...] The identity, which we ascribe to the mind of man, is only a fictitious one, and of like kind with that which we ascribe to vegetables and animal bodies.'²

Like the objects of these analogies, the self never requires any of its parts to stay constant throughout its existence. Nevertheless, we can always discover many relations between our perceptions:

'[T]he true idea of the human mind, is to consider it as a system of different perceptions or different existences, which are link'd together by the relation of cause and effect, and mutually produce, destroy, influence, and modify each other.'³

Impressions cause ideas and these, in turn, cause different passions and emotions which not only relate us to the past, but give us 'a present concern for our [...] future pains or pleasures.'⁴ It seems then, that the human mind is a tapestry composed of many interwoven threads, each one holding up the others. It is only because they are interconnected in these various ways that we regard them as one and the same thing, though really they're all distinct 'and therefore separable'. Once we have this notion of the self, we can add to it, even things which we have ourselves forgotten or perhaps never experienced in the first place:

'But having once acquir'd this notion of causation from the memory, we can extend the same chain of causes, and consequently the identity of our persons beyond our memory, and can comprehend times, and circumstances, and actions, which we have entirely forgot, but suppose in general to have existed.'⁵

Together, these relations of resemblance and causation are what lead us to attribute identity to ourselves.

1 Hume, *A Treatise of Human Nature*, 170.

2 Ibid., 169.

3 Ibid., 170.

4 Ibid.

5 Ibid., 170–71.

Why did Hume not simply adopt a Lockean theory of personal identity based on consciousness? Though we cannot discover an answer to this question in the *Treatise* itself, I believe that it had something to do with Hume's more thoroughgoing commitment to empiricism. The Lockean view of personal identity only works when we presuppose (if only hypothetically) a Cartesian soul which *may* think without knowing that it thinks. In this case *consciousness of thought* can function as a meaningful criterion for personal identity: that some thoughts are conscious makes them special and distinguishes them from others. However, this is an argument from above. As an empiricist, what he'd truly have to establish is how the idea of consciousness can be derived from experience itself. That is: How we can distinguish conscious thought from unconscious thought, knowing full well that all thoughts which we experience are conscious. This leads us back to Hume's problem, namely that in all experiences there is nothing common which we could call the self.

§11. *Penelhum's Objection*

In *Hume on Personal Identity*, Penelhum argues quite convincingly that Hume is mistaken in describing the identity of person as a natural fiction.¹ According to him, though Hume distinguishes between specific and numerical identity, he ends up confusing the two and thinks that 'for anything to be entitled to be called "the same" it has to remain *unchanged* from one period to the next.'² That this is not the case, he continues, can be easily understood if we carefully distinguish between the two different senses of identity:

'Now to remain unchanged is to remain the same in the *specific* sense, i.e., to be now exactly as one was at an earlier time. But I can remain the same in the *numerical* sense without doing so in the specific sense—I can be numerically the same but changed.'³

While I understand what Penelhum is aiming for—that is: to make it so that we are not continuously mistaken in our identity-statements—and agree with his argument in essence, I must correct him on his interpretation of Hume's relations of numerical and specific identity. What follows are these corrections and my own take on Penelhum's argument.

Despite what Penelhum believes, Hume's position and his own are not very different. First, let's distinguish two ways in which the distinction between numerical and

1 Penelhum, 'Hume on Personal Identity'.

2 *Ibid.*, 580.

3 *Ibid.*

specific identity can be understood. On the one hand, you have the ontological distinction, mirroring the distinction between substance and accident, where the numerical is taken to refer to an *actually* existing unchanging individual, and the specific to the variable properties of this something. Locke's definition of numerical identity, for example, relies on this ontology. On the other hand, you have the purely contingent or linguistic distinction between the numerical and specific which needn't necessarily line up with the ontological. In the case of Hume and Penelhum, these two meanings do not, in fact, agree. Hume, for one, denies that we have any positive idea of substance and he therefore cannot make any use of it in his philosophy, and while Penelhum does not explicitly take up an ontological position, he does not rely on the idea of substance in explaining numerical identity. This means that for them, numerical and specific identity in the contingent or linguistic sense both come down to specific identity in the ontological sense. The difference between Hume and Penelhum is how they define numerical identity. For Penelhum, numerical and specific identity are two partially overlapping domains: what is numerically identical is not necessarily specifically identical and what is specifically identical is not necessarily numerically identical. Hume, on the other hand, defines numerical identity as a very limited subdomain of specific identity. Whereas numerical identity involves 'the *invariableness* and *uninterruptedness* of any object, thro' a suppos'd variation of time',¹ specific identity involves only the former:

"Thus a man, who hears a noise, that is frequently interrupted and renew'd, says, it is still the same noise; tho' 'tis evident the sounds have only a specific identity or resemblance, and there is nothing numerically the same, but the cause, which produc'd them."²

On this account it is impossible for something to be numerically identical without being specifically identical, while the inverse remains possible. Given this definition of numerical identity, the above quote, 'for anything to be entitled to be called "the same" it has to remain *unchanged* from one period to the next', is entirely consistent and in fact unavoidable—despite what Penelhum claims, there's no confusion to speak of. Nevertheless, his criticism is in a certain sense correct. Hume's definition of identity appears to be a direct transcription of a combination Lockean-Leibnizean definition to a more thoroughgoing empiricism. Why? It seems as if Hume simply adapted an already popular definition of identity to his own philosophy. If this is true, then Penelhum's arguments will hit their mark a lot better if we interpret them to mean that Hume *shouldn't* have defined numerical identity in this manner. Hume's problem of 'fictitious identity' can be solved equally well by proposing a new definition of identity,

1 Hume, *A Treatise of Human Nature*, 134.

2 *Ibid.*, 168.

as long as this new definition is consistent with his empiricist theory of mind. This would have the desired effect of explaining the same identity-statements without attributing to people a psychological tendency to be continuously mistaken.

In reality, we'll be hard-pressed to find any one form of identity-condition which accounts for all identity-statements. But once we admit that there's no such thing as a substance which all numerical identity is intimately related to, and commit ourselves to the idea that our knowledge of objects does not need to correspond to an order of beings outside of perception, I see no problem in assuming there to be multiple different identity conditions related to different objects or object classes. All that is then required for us to know an individual is the ability, either explicitly or implicitly, to know an individuating feature.

Take Hume's example of a 'frequently interrupted and renew'd' noise, e.g., the ticking of a clock. Supposing that we have an empirical idea of duration—however imprecise—we can define the identity of the ticking as a noise n of duration d_1 , followed by a lack of noise of duration d_2 , so that $d_1(n)-d_2-d_1(n)-...$ would be a mock schema of the general idea of ticking. The simplest addition required to turn this into an expression of numerical identity is the condition that this expression must refer uniquely, i.e., that there is one and only one object which corresponds to it. In a case where we are confronted with two or more objects satisfying our schema, our expression simply ceases to refer.

This example is of little practical value, but like Hume, I'm mostly concerned with proving that this method is sound in principle, that it can in theory explain our identity-statements.¹

The ability to distinguish an individuating feature can either be implicit and psychological, which is supposedly most often the case—generally we don't really know how we distinguish one thing from another—or it can be explicit, through stipulation or the use of a definite description. Curiously, in these explicit cases, while the ideas are still 'fictions' in the Humean sense (as the manifold perceptions which make up the object are still distinct and separable and hence the idea of the object is not positively derived from experience), they are neither natural fictions, because they are not the result of a psychological tendency of the human mind; nor are they artificial fictions, if we associate these solely with fantastical creations entirely unrelated to perception.

§12. *The Appendix Aporia*

All's well that ends well—sadly Hume's theory of personal identity does not. Why is a

¹ My rejection of Hume's empiricist theory of sensation in §17 will make it difficult for me to consider this heavily reductionist notion of individuation as empirically correct.

matter of dispute. In the *Appendix* to the *Treatise* Hume famously claims his theory to be inconsistent or contradictory, but leaves the cause for this dissatisfaction underdetermined. The most popular interpretation frames this problem as a *problem of adequacy*:¹ Hume was dissatisfied with his solution because the fictitious identity of the self cannot be adequately explained using the proposed mechanisms of association.² But even amongst those who agree on this point, there is little consensus as to the particular nature of the problem which plagued the proposed solution and compelled Hume to reject it. Less popularly, the problem of the *Appendix* is interpreted as a *bundling problem*,³ a problem of how the impressions are first gathered together; or a *two minds problem*, a discrepancy between the metaphysical concept of mind which underlies the bulk of the *Treatise* and the philosophical concept of mind of Section 1.4.6—this is Galen Strawson's thesis.⁴ I will address only the first and last of these explanations. The bundling problem will be left out because I do not think there's any textual support for this interpretation. Hume's bundle of perceptions is a matter of fact. His question is never how the bundle comes about, this would be a metaphysical question, but how the separate and distinct perceptions can be joined together to create a fictitious unity. As an empirical fact, which is all that concerns us at the moment, the bundle undoubtedly exists.

I will first quote certain excerpts important to both interpretations:

[App1] 'But having thus loosen'd all our particular perceptions, when I proceed to explain the principle of connexion, which binds them together, and makes us attribute to them a real simplicity and identity; I am sensible that my account is very defective, and that nothing but the seeming evidence of the precedent reasonings⁵ cou'd have induc'd me to receive it.'⁶

[App2] 'But all my hopes vanish, when I come to explain the principles, that unite our successive perceptions in our thought or consciousness. I cannot discover any theory, which gives me satisfaction on this head.'⁷

[App3] 'In short there are two principles, which I cannot render consistent; nor is it in my power to renounce either of them, viz. *That all our distinct perceptions are distinct existences, and that the mind never perceives any real connexion among distinct existences.*'⁸

- 1 Strawson, *The Evident Connexion*, 117.
- 2 Brett, 'Substance and Mental Identity in Hume's *Treatise*'; Roth, 'What Was Hume's Problem with Personal Identity?'; Wolfram, 'Hume on Personal Identity'.
- 3 Strawson, *The Evident Connexion*, 120; Stroud, *Hume*, 118–40.
- 4 Strawson, *The Evident Connexion*. A similar argument is put forward by Patricia Kitcher. Kitcher, 'Kant on Self-Identity', 49, 63.
- 5 The arguments of Section 1.4.6.
- 6 Hume, *A Treatise of Human Nature*, 400.
- 7 Ibid.
- 8 Ibid.

[App4] ‘Did our perceptions either inhere in something simple and individual, or did the mind perceive some real connexion among them, there would be no difficulty in this case.’¹

Much has been made of these few sentences and I for one doubt that they provide enough information to settle the dispute one way or another. The explanations given are varied and diffuse, each differing greatly from the others, emphasising different words, relying on different sections, one conjecture stacked on top of the other. Some are plausible, others far-fetched, but all of them are problematic. Still, I can’t discuss Hume’s theory of personal identity without mentioning his self-confessed disappointment, for this reason I will briefly explain A. the ‘problem of adequacy’ and B. the ‘two minds problem’ interpretations. As to the truth of the matter: I leave that for the reader to decide.

A. THE PROBLEM OF ADEQUACY INTERPRETATION

What troubled Hume, according to most popular accounts, is that a shortcoming in the associative mechanisms of Section 1.4.6 prevents them from explaining the fictitious unity of the self. [App1], [App2] and [App3] all support this interpretation, though [App3] is hardly ever interpreted as saying that the two principles there referenced—‘*That all our distinct perceptions are distinct existences, and that the mind never perceives any real connexion among distinct existences.*’—are mutually inconsistent.² Instead, they are taken to be inconsistent with regard to a third factor. According to Brett, this third factor is their ability to form a perception of a single thing. ‘[W]here two (or more) things are contingently related, e.g., by a causal relation, they do not cease to be separate individuals [...] Hence, the associative connections among our perceptions can never be sufficient for regarding our ideas as combined into a single thing’.³ This argument is clearly faulty—the connections amongst different perceptions do not require the perceptions to cease being distinct existences—but is attributed to Hume under the assumption that he got caught up in the same metaphysics (of substance) he initially set out to reject.⁴

Roth’s diagnosis is more severe, the inconsistency detected by Hume is the result of a conflict between the operations of the mind in ascribing identity to objects, and those in ascribing identity to persons. His argument goes as follows:⁵

1 Hume, *A Treatise of Human Nature*, 400.

2 Roth, ‘What Was Hume’s Problem with Personal Identity?’, 110; Garrett, ‘Hume’s Self-Doubts about Personal Identity’, 339; Strawson, *The Evident Connexion*, 112.

3 Brett, ‘Substance and Mental Identity in Hume’s Treatise’, 124.

4 *Ibid.*, 125.

5 Roth, ‘What Was Hume’s Problem with Personal Identity?’

1. The Humean theory of identity is psychological.
2. It is a well-known tenet in Hume's psychology that two opposite tendencies of the mind interfere with each other.
3. Fictitious identity is the result of the mind mistaking strong associative relations for the subjective experience of real identity.
4. The perceptions which are associated are the same in objective and personal identity.
5. In order for us to experience different perceptions as perceptions of different objects, they must be experienced as interrupted and disjointed; in order for us to experience perceptions as perceptions of the self, they must be continuous and connected. These tendencies of the mind are opposed to each other.

Given a set of perceptions: P_1 , P_2 and P_3 ; if P_1 and P_2 are perceptions of object A , and P_3 is a perception of object B , then P_1 must be connected to P_2 by an associative relation, while neither P_1 nor P_2 can be connected to P_3 . However, for P_1 , P_2 and P_3 to be perceptions of the same self, it is required that all three of them are connected by associative relations—requirements inconsistent with those necessary for the identity of objects. This, according to Roth, is the inconsistency lamented in the *Appendix*.

Both Brett and Roth's explanations are unsatisfactory. Neither of them explain why this problem is specific to personal identity. In Brett's case, I fail to see how this same problem isn't also applicable to the identity of objects, it being equally true that a multitude of different perceptions are taken to be a single thing whilst simultaneously remaining distinct existences. In Roth's case, this problem also affects the perception of compound objects, e.g., in listening to a piece of music, the different notes are perceived as separate— $F\#$, A , G , $F\#$, $C\#$, ...—whilst still united by a common theme; in looking at a painting, the shapes are grasped as representing different objects, whilst still being parts of the same painting.

A regular shortcoming of problem of adequacy explanations is that they do not sufficiently account for [App4]. The metaphysical nature of Hume's solutions appears incompatible with his general philosophy. Arguably, the inconsistency which he discovered is not of a contingent, psychological nature. It is not a problem in explaining the self using the principles of association. In fact, even in the *Appendix*, Hume looks pleased with his psychological theory. His tone of writing implies a deeper problem inherent in explaining the use of these empirical relations themselves.

B. THE TWO MINDS PROBLEM INTERPRETATION

Strawson's reading of the *Appendix*, above called the 'two minds problem', is a bit more controversial. Contrary to most established interpretations, he claims that Hume is in fact a causal realist. Of course, he knows quite well that Hume denies the existence of an idea of real causation, but takes this to mean that we cannot know *what* this real causation is. It remains possible to postulate its existence, all the while maintaining that we can have no insight into its nature.

'Observed constant conjunction is *evidence* for existential dependency, i.e. real causal connection. But "we cannot penetrate into the reason of the conjunction".¹

This view he not only attributes to Hume, but is, according to him, 'taken for granted'² throughout the entirety of the *Treatise*. A similar view is expressed regarding the other principles of the imagination, viz. *resemblance* and *contiguity*. On the one hand they are theoretical and empirical concepts, referring to certain experiential relations; on the other, they are real deterministic connections which underlie the operations of the mind. The former are only possible as a result of the latter and provide evidence for the latter's existence. Corresponding to this split in the principles of the imagination—real vs. theoretical—is a split in our concept of mind: the mind as constitutive of our experiences, by means of the real associative relations [M1]; and the mind as an experiential fiction, the self of Section 1.4.6 [M2].

If this appears abstract and condensed, I must apologise, explaining it in full would require me to dedicate an entire section to this interpretation. Let us instead accept Strawson's premiss, however strange it may appear, and see where it takes us. Because, though there's much to be said against his causal realist interpretation, at present it has one strength: it is very good at explaining Hume's hopelessness in the *Appendix* and the ontological nature of [App4].

According to Strawson, the problem which Hume discovered was the existence of an 'unanswerable objection'³ which could be posed against his theory. Hume, in writing the *Treatise*, is committed to the maxim that all philosophical ideas must be derived from antecedent impressions. At the same time, he uses [M1] to explain the existence of certain perceptions, e.g., he must presuppose a real connection between different perceptions 'if there's to be any sense in which ideas derive from, or are copies of, or depend on, impressions'.⁴ Enter Section 1.4.6 and things go south: [M1] turns out not

1 Strawson, *The Evident Connexion*, 27.

2 *Ibid.*, 120.

3 *Ibid.*, 106.

4 *Ibid.*, 59.

to be an empirically warranted concept of mind, and [M2], which is empirically warranted, is not strong enough to take [M1]'s place—in fact, [M2] presupposes [M1]. This puts Hume in a unpleasant position; in order to save his theory he must explicitly assume one of [App4]'s metaphysical solutions: *Either* there is a simple and individual substance in which all our perceptions inhere (which means sacrificing [App3]'s 'distinct existences'), *or* there are real connections amongst our perceptions (which means sacrificing [App3]'s 'no real connections').¹ Neither of which are compatible with his empiricist commitments.

This is one of the most elegant solutions to the interpretative problem of the *Appendix*, but I cannot myself consent to it. I see no basis for a causal realist reading of Hume and the textual support put forward by Strawson is selective and could, for the most part, be chalked up to the 'ardor of youth' so often mentioned by Strawson himself.² For example, the dependence of ideas on impressions is a general rule which could just as easily be explained through purely experiential and empirical means, instead of presupposing a 'real connection'. Hume doesn't even regard this relation as infallible, but only says that the counterexamples are 'so particular and singular, that [they are] scarce worth our observing, and [do] not merit that for [them] alone we shou'd alter our general maxim.'³ Also, to say that Hume's philosophy does not exclude real causation in no way implies that Hume takes real causation 'for granted', what is necessary for Hume's philosophy is that experiences *are* ordered in a certain way, not that they must be so ordered—Strawson appears to give a transcendental interpretation of Hume's empiricism. For my part, I think it more likely, given Hume's moderate scepticism and the many passages warning philosophers not to suppose anything beyond what's given by experience, that he would take up an agnostic position. 'Nothing is more requisite for a true philosopher, than to restrain the intemperate desire of searching into causes, and having establish'd any doctrine upon a sufficient number of experiments, rest contented with that.'⁴

§13. *The Reflexivity of a Constructive Idea of Mind*

Quite separate from Hume's view on the matter, I cannot myself endorse a causal realist or constructive idea of mind such a Strawson proposes. On the presupposition that experience is our sole source of knowledge, it appears to me that any theory of mind which holds that experience is itself secondary to some other reality—whether spiritual

1 Strawson, *The Evident Connexion*, 106.

2 *Ibid.*, 17, 50, 125.

3 Hume, *A Treatise of Human Nature*, 10. I am convinced that this is mentioned somewhere in Strawson's *The Evident Connexion*, though I have since been unable to find it.

4 Hume, *A Treatise of Human Nature*, 14.

or material—is subject to the objection that in making this claim, they undermine the epistemological conditions necessary for us to have knowledge of this reality in the first place. This is not only true of Strawson’s interpretation of Hume, but of all empirical constructive theories of mind, such as, e.g., neuroscientific realism. I wish to advance two arguments against an empirical constructive idea of mind: First, that such a theory can never in fact be the result of any empirical investigation. Secondly, that if we presuppose the existence of something which causally determines experience, we cannot possibly know whether our knowledge of this object actually corresponds to the object in question.

First, that it cannot be the result of an empirical investigation can be shown on the basis of R.B. Perry’s arguments in *The Ego-Centric Predicament*. Perry takes perception (or experience) to consist in a relation of perceiving between a subject and an object, this is by him expressed as $(E)R^c(T)$, where (E) stands for ‘ego’ and (T) for ‘everything’ or ‘thing’.¹ In what follows, I will leave out the (E) and treat R^c as a function with an input T , such that $experience = R^c(T)$.

I will use causal brain processes—from the perspective of a possible constructive idea of mind—as a representative instance of R^c . For us to know R^c , we would have to compare T as part of $R^c(T)$, with T separate from this function. That is: we must know the input and the output in order to have a chance of figuring out what happens in between. (In our case: we would have to know how an object is before being processed by the brain and compare this with our experience of it after being processed.) But exactly this way of knowing an object, as a T separate from R^c , an object distinct from our particular way of perceiving it, is excluded by the premiss that all experience is $R^c(T)$ and that all knowledge is empirical;² knowledge of R^c is in principle impossible.

If we wish to know anything about the brain, we can only approach it as an object of experience, that is: $R^c(brain)$. This gives us no insight into the relation R^c by which the brain supposedly determines experience, but only of the experience of the brain as it-self determined by R^c . (Compare this to §15.C.)

The only relations which we can discover between the brain and other phenomena are empirical in kind. As with all experiential objects, when we perceive a frequent conjunction of two or more phenomena, for example: visual stimulation, neural activity and visual perception (e.g., a red light); we can generally assume that one of them depends on the other(s). This relation can be represented in the following manner: $R^c(\text{visual stimulation}) \rightarrow R^c(\text{neural activity}) \rightarrow R^c(\text{red light})$. Our experience of a visual stimulus (or rather, the experimenter’s knowledge that the participant is exposed to visual stimulation) is succeeded by the experience of neural activity (an fMRI image on a

1 Perry, ‘The Ego-Centric Predicament’, 5–6.

2 Ibid., 8.

screen opposite the experimenter) which is in turn succeeded by a certain visual perception (the participant seeing the red light). Even in the case of experiments in cognitive neuroscience, we will only discover empirical relations and at no point do we have insight into the true nature of the function R^c .

Secondly, granting for a moment that there is something which determines our experience, it would follow that we can have no knowledge of this object. For the sake of our argument, we'll again take the brain to be the hypothetical cause responsible for shaping experience. I'll express the difference between the (experiential or) 'phenomenal' and 'real' use of the concept brain with a subscript P or R. As I said during the previous argument, our knowledge of the brain_P is knowledge of the brain as an experiential object_P. That is: as a perception it_P is already processed by the brain_R. Even though the idea that we have knowledge of the 'real' brain_R by examining the experiential brain_P is thoroughly mistaken, we will nonetheless suppose that this is exactly what happens and that by experimenting on the brain_P we can discover the conditions of experience in general (brain_R).

We are now faced with a curious case of an object that can only be known insofar as it lets itself to be known. The brain_R itself determines how the brain_P is perceived. How can we be sure that what it_R shows us is actually reliable? In this case, an appeal to experience cannot be permitted, that would be like establishing the truth of a story on the self-asserted credibility of the narrator—what if the narrator isn't to be trusted? (Or, as Wittgenstein puts it: 'As if someone were to buy several copies of the morning paper to assure himself that what it said was true.')

To drive this point home: We can revisit the depths of Cartesian doubt and imagine that all our experiences are simply the result of an evil genius's will. Every one of our experiments would come out just the same, the experiential causal connections remain, yet our brain would not be the source of our knowledge—the evil genius is. This should indicate that the premisses do not entail the conclusion. Somewhere there must have been a curious leap of faith which leads us from the experiential relations between the brain_P and other phenomena, to the conclusion that the brain_R is the real cause of consciousness or experience.

1 Wittgenstein, *Philosophical Investigations*, 79.

Chapter 4

Kant¹

§14. Synthetic Judgements A Priori

Kant's concept of self differs greatly from both the rationalist ego of Descartes and the empiricist selves of Locke and Hume. It is heavily marked by his transcendental method; in fact, his I is a transcendental concept, indispensable to his philosophical system.

What does it mean to be transcendental? In broad terms we can define *transcendental* as an adjective denoting something to be an absolutely necessary condition for the possibility of experience in general.² Accordingly, a transcendental philosophy is one whose sole concern is the discovery of these fundamental conditions. The I is of such importance: it is the necessary unity which we must presuppose in all our thinking. Contrary to Descartes, it is nothing but a subjective condition of thought and gives us no knowledge of objective existences. Contrary to Locke and Hume, it is not given in or constructed through sensible intuition.

To explain how he arrives at this peculiar concept, we must turn to the *Critique of Pure Reason*, more specifically Section 2 of Chapter 2 of the *Transcendental Analytic: Transcendental deduction of the pure concepts of understanding* (from now on: *Transcendental Deduction*, or simply *Deduction*); and Chapter 1 of the *Transcendental Dialectic: The paralogisms of pure reason* (from now on: *Paralogisms*). (§§15 and 16 respectively.) In the *Transcendental Deduction* he first introduces his concept of self and distinguishes it from the empirical self of inner intuition; in the *Paralogisms* he uses this new concept to criticise the rationalist attempts at deducing the true nature of the self from the purely intellectual 'I think'.

The *Transcendental Deduction* plays an important part in answering the central question of the *Critique of Pure Reason*: 'How are synthetic judgments *a priori* possible?'³ In this introductory section, I will try to clarify the meaning of this question and how it relates to the *Deduction*. First, what does Kant mean by 1. Synthesis (and analysis), and; 2. *a priori* (and *a posteriori*)?

¹ All references to the *Critique of Pure Reason* will follow the A/B pagination.

² Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, A11=B25.

³ *Ibid.*, B19.

The relation of the subject to the predicate of a judgement can be of two kinds: it can either be *analytic* or *synthetic*.¹ If it is *analytic*, the predicate of the judgement is already contained in the concept of the subject; if it is *synthetic*, the predicate of the judgement lies outside of the concept of the subject and relates to it, as it were, from without.² Analytic judgements are generally used to clarify concepts, e.g., a triangle has three corners. (As we will see shortly, this particular example is also an a priori judgement.) Synthetic judgements, on the other hand, are the only way by which we can expand our knowledge and can join unrelated concepts together. E.g., the triangle is green.

Judgements can also be distinguished as to their origin: they can either be *a priori* or *a posteriori*. An *a priori* judgement is one that does not depend on experience for its truth; an *a posteriori* judgement is one that is only possible by virtue of experience and in reference to what is empirically given.³ The analytic judgement 'a triangle has three corners' is true a priori since it merely expresses the meaning of the concept, it does not depend on the actual existence or perception of a triangle. The synthetic judgement 'the triangle is green' can only be true a posteriori, if there is an empirical perception of a triangle which is simultaneously the perception of a green thing.

When we ask ourselves what is necessary for a synthetic a priori judgement, one thing becomes clear: the synthesis of the two concepts cannot depend on the concepts alone. By justifying the possibility of synthetic a priori judgements, Kant wishes to demonstrate the possibility of pure mathematics and pure natural science. He wishes to prove that, e.g., it is an a priori and necessary truth that the sum of the angles of a triangle equals 180 degrees. The *understanding*, as the source of all concepts and the faculty of rules, thinking, and judging, cannot by itself establish this to be the case.⁴ The concept triangle does not contain within itself the concept 180 degrees. Of course, we can always create a complex concept, e.g., we can combine the idea of a triangle with the idea of 180 degrees in the concept of a triangle the sum of whose angles is 180 degrees, and this concept can even be true (as it is in the present case). But though we know it to be true, its truth cannot depend on the concepts alone. This new concept allows us to say that the sum of the angles of a triangle, the sum of whose angles is 180 degrees, is 180 degrees—an analytic judgement which is trivially true, but this is obviously not what we are looking for. We wish to establish that a triangle, any triangle that can be intuitively given to us, will necessarily have 180 degrees as the sum of its angles. This requires the concepts of triangle and 180 degrees to be in some way given

1 This should be carefully distinguished from Descartes' use of these terms (p. 11).

2 Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, A6–7=B10–11.

3 Ibid., B2.

4 Ibid., A80–81=B106, A132=B171.

together, both represented at the same time. To accomplish this the understanding does not suffice, we need intuition.

Intuition is the way in which objects are given to us for cognition (knowledge).¹ Though we are generally inclined to equate intuition with sensible intuition, i.e., empirical perception, this is not the only kind of intuition possible. If it were, we'd be in big trouble: in order to prove that the sum of the angles of a triangle must necessarily be 180 degrees, it does not suffice that I prove it to be true of one triangle, by measuring its angles and discovering them to be ~180 degrees. Not even by measuring a thousand triangles will I know this to be a necessary property of theirs. Such necessity requires that I relate the concept of triangle, not to what is actually given in empirical intuition, but to what can possibly be given in intuition in general. I must prove that this particular property of triangles is a result of the form of intuition itself. That the idea of a triangle whose angles do not add up to 180 degrees is not by itself contradictory can be proven by the fact that we can consistently think about them within certain non-euclidean geometries. The only reason why we say that the sum of the angles of a triangle is 180 degrees, is because our intuition of space is the intuition of an euclidean space. This form of intuition must be anterior to empirical intuition and is the condition of synthetic a priori judgements. The existence of pure intuition is ostensibly proven in the *Transcendental Aesthetic*,² but this is of little interest to us.

What does concern us is the following: Even if we have a concept of a triangle and a concept of 180 degrees, how can I know that something corresponding to these concepts can actually be given in intuition? Of course, I know that they can because I can draw a triangle on a piece of paper and can measure the angles with a protractor, but how is this to be justified a priori? Intuition furnishes us with a manifold of spatial locations and temporal moments, a manifold and nothing but a manifold. Through intuition colours, tastes, smells, and other sensations may be given to me, but nothing else—it is not a form of thinking but a form of perceiving, a receptivity to sensations. (Remember Descartes' wax, p.14.) The understanding, on the other hand, though it thinks, is not a form of intuition. It is not itself receptive to sensations. We must therefore ask ourselves: by what right do we apply the concepts of understanding to intuition? Is the correspondence between thought and intuition purely accidental? If this is the case, then the possibility of synthetic a priori judgements seems difficult to justify. How can I know that the faculty of understanding can be applied to intuition at all? This is the question of the *Transcendental Deduction* and it is in this context that Kant's concept of self first emerges.

1 Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, A19=B33.

2 Ibid., A19–49=B33–73.

§15. *The Transcendental Deduction*

The argument of the *Transcendental Deduction*, insofar as it concerns the transcendental apperception, can be distinguished into three parts: A. The analytical unity of apperception; B. the synthetic unity of apperception, and; C. the distinction between the I of the apperception and the empirical I of inner intuition. As the arguments of A and B can be blindingly difficult, I will first describe their general structure before elaborating on each part.

First, the *analytical unity of apperception* is expressed by Kant as follows:

“The **I think** must **be able** to accompany all my representations; for otherwise something would be represented in me that could not be thought at all, which is as much as to say that the representation would either be impossible or else at least would be nothing for me.”¹

We can interpret this as saying that I can only discover myself as a continuously existing self insofar as I can gather all the different representations given to me in intuition into one consciousness, for if a representation cannot be gathered into this one consciousness, it cannot be said to be mine. That is to say: the identity of a subject presupposes that all its representations are given as a unity, which for Kant is the same as to say that they must be represented in *one* experience.

Secondly, every analysis presupposes a synthesis. The one experience which all our perceptions belong to can be analysed and distinguished into many different representations. E.g., when looking at the book that’s in front of me, I can distinguish the blue of its cover from the white of its pages. The fact that I can distinguish these different perceptions in this one experience means that these different perceptions must have been joined together at some point—only by joining the different parts together can they ever constitute a whole.

Thirdly, the only faculty capable of combining different representations is the understanding (in thinking and judging). Intuition merely presents us with a manifold of different perceptions. For them to be given in one experience (the necessity of which is expressed in the analytical unity) they must be combined together. It follows that the manifold of intuition must be united by the understanding. This act of combining the different perceptions given in intuition is the *synthetic unity of apperception*. Because of this synthetic unity of apperception, the combining of the manifold of intuition in accordance with the categories, our concepts of understanding must necessarily be applicable to intuition and the goal of the *Deduction* is reached.

¹ Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, B131–32.

A. THE ANALYTICAL UNITY OF APPERCEPTION

'The I think must be able to accompany all my representations'. At this point in the *Deduction* (§§16–17) Kant is dealing with the analytical unity of apperception and this sentence should be interpreted as an analytic judgement: the 'must be able to accompany all my representations' is already contained in the concept of the 'I think'.¹

Kant's 'I think' is synonymous with apperception.² The 'I' refers to the necessity of a (subjective) unity in thinking. A thought (cognition) always contains multiple representations within itself and we can imagine all these representations as separate entities. For example, in the judgement 'the car is red', we can distinguish 'car' and 'red' and each of these can be thought as distinct from the other. It is however impossible to think of a thought or judgement without thinking of the different representations as united in the same subject. Both 'car' and 'red', as combined in this judgement, must belong to me—they must both be *my* representations. While the thought can be represented as a manifold, I as a subject can never experience myself as anything but a simple and singular existence³ to whom this manifold must be related. This is not only a condition for particular judgements, but of all experience whatsoever, at least insofar as it concerns *my* experience.

'[O]nly because I can comprehend their manifold in a consciousness do I call them all together **my** representations; for otherwise I would have as multicolored, diverse a self as I have representations of which I am conscious.'⁴

We can better understand what Kant is getting at by taking into account, for a moment, his theory of sensation. (This will be treated more extensively in §17.) According to Kant, our sensations are given as a succession of momentary impressions,⁵ each one unrelated to the others. For example, when looking at a painting, the totality of sensations must be gone through sequentially in order to establish the entire picture,⁶ but none of these sensations by themselves imply any of the others. If this is true, then

1 Ibid., B138.

2 Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, B137.

3 Ibid., A354–55.

4 Ibid., B134.

5 Ibid., A99.

6 'My mind is always busy with forming the image of the manifold while it goes through [it]. [...] Therefore if a human being comes into a room which is piled high with pictures and decorations, then he can make no image of it, because his mind cannot run through the manifold. It does not know from which end it should begin in order to illustrate the object. So it is reported that when a stranger enters St. Peter's church in Rome, he is wholly disconcerted on account of the manifold splendor. The cause is: his soul cannot go through the manifold in order to illustrate it.' Kant, *Lectures on Metaphysics*, 54.

what is originally given by the senses must be a strobe light of disconnected sensations, resembling the stream of consciousness in modernist writing. E.g.,

‘Where there was roughness of fabric all was smooth with a smoothness and firm rounded pressing and a long warm coolness, cool outside and warm within, long and light and closely holding, closely held, lonely, hollow-making with contours, happy-making, young and loving and now all warmly smooth with a hollowing, chest-aching, tight-held loneliness’¹

Each flash of sensation could just as well have been an entirely different consciousness, there is no constancy, no unity between them. But insofar as there is an ‘I think’, and these sensations and manifold representations are joined into a continuous experience or an empirical perception of an object, they must be united, they must all be related to one consciousness—i.e., mine.

It is noted by Ewing that the unity of consciousness implies a correlative unity of experience, a unity in the world—you can’t have one without the other.² I can only *discover* myself as a continuously existing self insofar as I can gather all the different representations given to me in intuition into one experience; for if a representation cannot be gathered into this one experience, and is disjointed from every other representation, it can have no meaning to me and cannot be said to be mine. Compare this to someone who has momentary thought which, one instant later, he forgets all about. This thought, being unrelated to every other of his experiences, makes up no part of his world and the consciousness by which it was grasped might equally well have never existed.

‘There is only **one** experience, in which all perceptions are represented as in thoroughgoing and lawlike connection, just as there is only one space and time, in which all forms of appearance and all relation of being or non-being take place.’³

This dual relationship between subject and object is easily misunderstood. Carr, for example, interpreted it to mean that ‘[t]he “I think” is not the object of a representation, but accompanies representations as their subject. Like Husserl’s transcendental ego, it is nothing apart from its intentional relations to the world.’⁴ This however significantly misshapes Kant’s argument. To my knowledge, Husserl did not regard the I (or ‘ego’) as a unity in thought which functioned as the merely logical correlate to the unity

1 Hemingway, *For Whom the Bell Tolls*, 74.

2 Ewing, ‘Kant’s Transcendental Deduction of the Categories’. See also: Dewey, ‘On Some Current Conceptions of the Term “Self”’, 58–59.

3 Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, A110.

4 Carr, ‘Kant, Husserl, and the Nonempirical Ego’, 688.

THE TRANSCENDENTAL DEDUCTION

of experience, but as a 'directional structure that goes towards what is presented'¹ and can be discovered by, as it were, reversing the arrow, following the intentional act in the opposite direction. The same cannot be said of Kant:

'The latter relation [the identity of the subject] therefore does not yet come about by my accompanying each representation with consciousness, but rather by my **adding** one representation to the other and being conscious of their synthesis.'²

For Kant, the I is the qualitative unity in thinking and can only be thought by a corresponding unity in experience. As I have mentioned already and will become clearer when we get to the synthetic unity of apperception, the relation of the subject to the object which is a condition for there to be a subject at all, is one of constructing the object, of joining the different representations which compose the object together. The Kantian subject is not something immanent in every singular act of consciousness, as an 'ego-center',³ but is the logical unity which we must presuppose in the combination of our representations.

Every analysis presupposes a synthesis and is only possible because of this synthesis.⁴ When I look at a chair, I am really looking at a complex object composed of many different parts: it has four legs, a seat, a back. The fact that I can distinguish these parts means that they must, at some point, have been joined together. It is not merely required that I am conscious of each of them, but that I am conscious of all of them simultaneously. The same goes for experience in general. The one experience which all perceptions belong to, which can be derived from the analytical unity of apperception, presupposes a synthetic unity of apperception—an act of combining.⁵

B. THE SYNTHETIC UNITY OF APPERCEPTION

Intuition presents us with a manifold of perceptions. A manifold of different spatial locations and temporal moments and, in the case of empirical intuition: colours, sounds, feelings, etc. Nothing else is given besides this manifold and this manifold should be regarded as a loose aggregate rather than an ordered whole. For these perceptions to be combined something more is needed, something which can establish a unity amongst the representations. The understanding, as the faculty of thought and judgement, is the only faculty capable of doing this. The forms of judgement are the

1 Husserl, *Analyses Concerning Passive and Active Synthesis*, 17.

2 Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, B133.

3 Husserl, *Analyses Concerning Passive and Active Synthesis*, 17.

4 Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, B130.

5 *Ibid.*, B135.

only forms of combination and the categories of understanding, which are derived from these forms of judgement, are the pure concepts of synthesis, the concepts which correspond to the unity thought in the judgements.¹

The synthetic unity of apperception refers to the act of combining the manifold of intuition in accordance with the categories. However, in the same way that intuition requires something outside of itself to combine its manifold representations; the categories of understanding, as pure concepts of unity, require something outside of themselves for their application. “Thoughts without content are empty, intuitions without concepts are blind.”² Each needs the other to be in any sense meaningful.

In order to apply the categories of understanding to intuition, they must somehow be made sensible. This requires the imagination, which is homogeneous with both thought and intuition, to function as a mediating faculty.³ Of the two forms of intuition, time and space, time is the more general one.⁴ (We can imagine non-spatial phenomena, such as affections, but we cannot imagine atemporal phenomena.) For the categories of understanding to be applicable to all intuitions in general, they must therefore be related to time. The imagination determines intuition by means of time-determinations, specific relations in time which correspond to the categories. In joining together the manifold representations of intuition, the imagination is subject to these temporal-determinations and can effect a unity in experience in accordance with the categories of understanding.

C. PURE SELF VS. EMPIRICAL SELF

§§24 and 25 of the *Transcendental Deduction* introduce an important distinction into Kant’s theory of self, namely that between the pure ego of the transcendental apperception and the empirical ego of inner sense. The ‘I’ of the ‘I think’, is in no way intuitively given to us, ‘But this representation [“I think”] is an act of **spontaneity**, i.e., it cannot be regarded as belonging to sensibility’,⁵ and must carefully be distinguished from the way we know ourselves, the psychological self-image we have of ourselves as something with a history, a body, a personality—the self as concerned Locke and Hume.

From the beginning of the *Critique of Pure Reason*, this latter concept of self, the empirical self, is associated with inner sense or time. Contrary to space which, as outer sense, merely concerns external appearances, inner sense is the medium by which we

1 Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, A78–79=B104.

2 Ibid., A51=B75.

3 Ibid., A78=B103, B151–52.

4 Ibid., A139=B178.

5 Ibid., B132.

intuit the self or soul.¹ Note that many phenomena which we ordinarily relate to the self can only be described using temporal relations.² However, because this self is given in intuition, it is a mere appearance and already requires the transcendental apperception. For us to be able to know ourselves as an empirical self, it is required that there is a unity in the manifold of intuition, which presupposes the synthetic unity of apperception. The 'I' of the 'I think' cannot be the same 'I' as the psychological ego. (When perceiving myself in intuition, I, as a subject, cognise myself as an object.)³

Though the I of the apperception plays an important role in making intuition intelligible, by determining it in accordance with the categories, it cannot itself be made intuitible. It remains 'behind the scenes'. An example given by Kant to illustrate this fact is the drawing of a line in the imagination.⁴ When we do so, it requires us to determine different points in space in accordance with the concept of a line. That is to say: we must successively add bits of space together, synthetically combine them, in order to apprehend them as constituting a single object. Notice that, although we end up with the intuition of a line, we do not intuit the synthetic act necessary to present this line to ourselves. The result of the apperception is given, the apperception itself is not.

'I exist as an intelligence that is merely conscious of its faculty for combination but which, in regard to the manifold that it is to combine, is subject to a limiting condition that it calls inner sense, which can make that combination intuitible only in accordance with temporal relations that lie entirely outside of the concepts of the understanding proper, and that can therefore still cognize itself merely as it appears to itself with regard to an intuition [...]'⁵

We can only know the I of the transcendental apperception as it determines intuition, not as it is in itself: a determining.

'Now I do not have yet another self-intuition, which would give the **determining** in me, of the spontaneity of which alone I am consciousness, even before the act of **determination**, in the same way as time gives that which is to be determined, thus I cannot determine my existence as that of a self-active being, rather I merely represent the spontaneity of my thought, i.e., of the determining, and my existence always remains only sensibly determinable, i.e., determinable as the existence of an appearance.'⁶

1 Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, A34=B50–51.

2 E.g. the feeling of pleasure: 'The consciousness of the causality of a representation with respect to the state of the subject, **for maintaining** it in that state, can here designate in general what is called pleasure'. Kant, *Critique of the Power of Judgment*, 105.

3 Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, B155.

4 Ibid., B154.

5 Ibid., B158–59.

6 Ibid., B157–58.

This prevents Kant from taking up the Cartesian standpoint that the self can have objective knowledge of its own existence through the purely intellectual ‘I think’. Knowledge is only possible as the correspondence between a concept and intuition; knowledge of myself is accordingly only possible by means of an intuitive representation of myself.

§16. *The Paralogisms*

The *Paralogisms*-chapter, though located some 200+ pages after the end of the *Deduction*, depends heavily on the arguments and conclusions there presented. Contrary to the *Transcendental Deduction*, this chapter does not concern the *understanding*, the faculty of rules, thinking and judging, but *reason*, the faculty of inferences.¹ In particular, here and throughout the entirety of the *Transcendental Dialectic* (to which the present chapter belongs), he is concerned with the *fallacious and transgressive use of reason*—the use of reason beyond the bounds of possible knowledge.² Otherwise put: he investigates how discursive thought, by a very convincing illusion, can lead us to believe that we have knowledge of existences which are not and cannot be given in sensible intuition. As regards the *Paralogisms*, the existence which concerns Kant is the I or self.

What is the purpose of the Paralogisms? In the *Paralogisms* Kant criticises the pretension of rational psychology³ that the nature of the self can be deduced from nothing but the ‘I think’ of the transcendental apperception.⁴ Most likely, the main targets of this critique were Descartes and Leibniz.⁵ There are four paralogisms in total: a paralogism ‘of substantiality’, ‘of simplicity’, ‘of personality’ and ‘of ideality’.⁶ Each represents a rationalist argument used to attribute certain properties to the self. For example, the paralogism of substantiality is used to prove the immateriality of the soul.⁷ The purpose of the *Paralogisms* is not to reject wholesale all uses of the categories in relation to the self, but rather to criticise the tendency of rational psychology to attribute objective value to what are essentially subjective conditions of thought. E.g., we can rightfully say that the self is simple, if by this we mean that all representations must be related to one consciousness (an absolute logical unity); however, we cannot say that there exists an object which corresponds to this unity, since the unity is merely *thought* in the

1 Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, A330=B386.

2 Ibid., A295=B352.

3 Ibid., A334=B391.

4 Ibid., A342=B400.

5 Kitcher, ‘Kant’s Paralogisms’, 516.

6 Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, A348–66.

7 Ibid., A345=B403.

THE PARALOGISMS

concept of the self, while objective knowledge of its existence requires it to be given in intuition.¹

What is a paralogism? A paralogism can be defined as a sophistical syllogism with correct premisses but an incorrect conclusion due to an equivocal middle term.² A rather silly example:

[Major] All laws are enforceable.
[Minor] The excluded middle is a law.
[Conclusion] Therefore the excluded middle is enforceable.

In the major, 'laws' is interpreted as positive laws, the binding laws of a certain society. In the minor, 'law' is interpreted as a logical rule or principle, a law of thought. Despite having the appearance of a proper syllogism, the argument is obviously nonsensical—no one has ever been arrested for breaking the law of excluded middle. We can represent the form of a paralogism as follows:

[Major] All A are B.
[Minor] All C are D.
[Conclusion] Therefore all C are B.

It is clear that even if both premisses are true, we cannot validly infer that the conclusion is true. According to Kant, the principal arguments of rational psychology are of this form.

I will not treat each paralogism separately but will focus on the first (of substantiality) which will function as a generic representative for the others. The nature of the equivocal middle term is the same in each one.

The paralogism of substantiality, A-version:

[Major] That the representation of which is the **absolute subject** of our judgments, and hence cannot be used as the determination of another thing, is **substance**.
[Minor] I, as a thinking being, am the **absolute subject** of all my possible judgments, and this representation of Myself cannot be used as the predicate of any other thing.
[Conclusion] Thus I, as thinking being (soul), am **substance**.³

B-version:

[Major] **What cannot be thought otherwise than as subject does not exist otherwise than as subject, and is therefore substance.**

- 1 Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, A354–55.
- 2 Ibid., A402; Proops, 'Kant's First Paralogism', 468.
- 3 Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, A348.

[Minor] **Now a thinking being, considered merely as such, cannot be thought otherwise than as subject.**

[Conclusion] **Therefore it also exists only as such a thing, i.e., as substance.**¹

The middle term of this syllogism is '[w]hat cannot be thought otherwise than as subject', or in the A-version '[t]hat the representation of which is the absolute subject of our judgments'. Why is this equivocal? The reason given by Kant is the following:

'The major premise talks about a being that can be thought of in every respect, and consequently even as it might be given in intuition. But the minor premise talks about this being only insofar as it is considered as subject, relative only to thinking and the unity of consciousness, but not at the same time in relation to the intuition through which it is given as an object for thinking.'²

This mirrors §§24 and 25 of the *Deduction* on the distinction between the self of the apperception and the empirical self of intuition (§15.C). Though both the origin and meaning of the major are disputed,³ we can argue that Kant was mostly interested in establishing '[w]hat cannot be thought otherwise than as a subject' as a condition for applying the category of substance to an intuition. That is to say: it refers to the (possible) objective use of the category. The emphasis laid on the difference between

1 Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, B410–11.

It has been remarked by Proops that neither the A nor the B-version adhere to proper syllogistic form and, for the sake of clarity, can be rewritten as:

[Major] All entities that cannot be thought otherwise than as subjects are entities that cannot exist otherwise than as subject, and therefore (by definition) are substances.

[Minor] All entities that are thinking beings are entities that cannot be thought otherwise than as subjects.

[Conclusion] Therefore: All entities that cannot be thought otherwise than as subjects are entities that cannot exist otherwise than as subject, and therefore (by definition) are substances.

Proops, 'Kant's First Paralogism', 470–71, 478.

2 Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, B411. This is inconsistent with the answer given in the A-version: 'the major premise makes a merely transcendental use of the category, in regard to its condition, but [...] the minor premise and the conclusion, in respect of the soul that is subsumed under this condition, make an empirical use of the same category.' (Ibid., A402.) I will use the B-version as the answer of the A-version makes very little sense. the category is not the middle term of the syllogism and the minor does not make empirical use of the category. In fact, the category is not even part of the minor. If the minor were interpreted as an empirical proposition it wouldn't be true, which would make the argument not only formally, but also materially false.

3 Proops, 'Kant's First Paralogism', 472; Kitcher, 'Kant's Paralogisms', 518–19; Ameriks, *Kant's Theory of Mind: An Analysis of the Paralogisms of Pure Reason*, xxix.

thought and cognition in the paragraphs immediately preceding the paralogisms⁴ supports this interpretation, as does the footnote at B411–12:

“Thinking” is taken in an entirely different signification in the two premises: in the major premise, as it applies to an object in general (hence as it may be given in intuition); but in the minor premise only as it subsists in relation to self-consciousness, where, therefore, no object is thought, but only the relation to oneself as subject (as the form of thinking) is represented.¹

In the major premiss, thinking relates to possible intuition and is supposedly the schema of substance, i.e., the temporal determination by virtue of which the concept of substance can be made intuitable. In the minor premiss, thinking refers to the ‘I think’ of apperception. If the minor is to be true, the middle term must here be taken to mean that the I ‘cannot be thought otherwise than as subject’ in the analytic sense discussed above (§15.A): ‘The I think must be able to accompany all my representations’. Accordingly, the middle term is here interpreted as analytically contained within the ‘I think’: we must necessarily think the self as substance because all our thoughts, all our use of the categories, are necessarily related to the ‘I think’. The categories already presuppose that all the representations which I combine in thinking are *my* representations.

‘For this inner perception is nothing beyond the mere apperception I think, which even makes all transcendental concepts possible, which say “I think substance, cause, etc.”’²

Contrary to the major premiss, which establishes the objective use of the category, the minor only establishes its subjective use: we must think the self as the absolute subject of all our representations (and to this extent it is substance), but we can never know the self to actually be substance as this would require it to be given in sensible intuition—something which is precluded by the fact that the self is a mere unity in thought and, as the determining, precedes everything that is determinable (§15.C).

‘Meanwhile, one can quite well allow the proposition **The soul is substance** to be valid, if only one admits that this concept of ours leads no further, that it cannot teach us any of the usual conclusions of the rationalistic doctrine of the soul, such as, e.g., the everlasting duration of the soul through all alterations, even the human being’s death, thus that it signifies a substance only in the idea but not in reality.’³

4 Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, 406–07.

1 Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, B411–12.

2 Ibid., A343=B401.

3 Ibid., A350–51.

The same equivocation is true of all the paralogisms: the objective use of a category in the major is confused with the subjective use of this category in the minor (where it is merely *thought* as a determination of the self) and the conclusion wrongfully claims to have objective knowledge of the nature of the self.

§17. Sensation and Experience

So far I've discussed rather uncritically the belief by Locke, Hume and Kant that the building blocks of our experiences are singular and indivisible sensations. This position is logically appealing: We distinguish the chair into its component parts, e.g., legs, seat, back, and discover that each of these components can be further separated into smaller parts and these, again, into parts of ever-increasing minuteness. Because the existence of the whole depends on the existence of its parts, it is not possible that this discrimination should go on indefinitely; we must necessarily suppose there to be certain smallest or simplest parts which we call sensations and which, in their different combinations, constitute perception. But despite the rationality of this argument, the existence of these simplest sensations appears contrary to all experience. When we first meet an object, we often experience it 'in one go', without any separation. It is only later, when we approach it more attentively, with 'an eye for detail', that its many parts become apparent to us. Does this mean that in first perceiving it, these parts were already present, albeit in a latent fashion? If latent is taken to mean dimly, then this can certainly be the case—a dim awareness is still an awareness. But it does not appear that such a dim awareness of all the constitutive parts is necessary for us to experience an object. If latent is taken to mean potentially, then it is certainly true that an awareness can contain an expectation of these parts, but an expectation is not itself an awareness or cognition. (An expectation can be disappointed.) If, finally, latent is taken to mean that these parts are actually perceived, but we are not consciously aware of them, then I can only take this to mean that they can, at a later point in time, or in an indirect manner, be brought to consciousness through remembrance, association or inference from another experience.¹ In the latter case, we cannot be said to have experienced anything directly, and in the former it is only at that moment, when we become aware of the parts, that they are then first experienced. Experience is not a necessary correlate to our brain processes (or the actions of the soul, in Cartesian philosophy), so while our brain might register some of the object's parts, and they may

¹ Resembling cases of unconscious 'perception' such as discussed in: Haynes and Rees, 'Predicting the Orientation of Invisible Stimuli from Activity in Human Primary Visual Cortex'; Marcel, 'Conscious and Unconscious Perception: Experiments on Visual Masking and Word Recognition'; Calvert et al., 'Activation of Auditory Cortex during Silent Lipreading'.

then become present in some other or later experience, this unconscious 'perception' is a purely physical causal process and not present in experience itself. Empirically it seems more proper to say that the whole is related to its parts in a temporally extended manner, the whole *becomes* distinguished into parts by virtue of a discriminating activity.

The purpose of the present section is, on the one hand, to criticise the supposition made by the Descartes, Locke, Hume and Kant, that the experience of a complex object is itself a complex experience and, on the other hand, to call into question the Kantian idea that analysis presupposes synthesis. This second point of course depends on the first. Given that the pure ego in Kantian philosophy is nothing but the unity necessary to join the manifold sensations in accordance with the categories of the understanding, *if there is no reason to presuppose that there is such a manifold of unrelated sensations, then there is no reason to presuppose the existence of a pure ego.*

Locke, Berkeley and Hume all took sensations to be *minima sensibilia*: the smallest discernible parts of perception.¹ Locke's temporal 'moments' and Hume's atomic sensible points can here serve as examples. The experiential nature of these smallest parts means that, by an admittedly strenuous act of attention, we should be able to become aware of them or have some direct indication of their existence. An argument to this end can be found in Section 1.2.4 of Hume's *Treatise*:

'Put a spot of ink upon paper, and retire to such a distance, that the spot becomes altogether invisible; you will find, that upon your return and nearer approach the spot first becomes visible by short intervals; and afterwards becomes always visible; and afterwards acquires only a new force in its colouring without augmenting its bulk; and afterwards, when it has increas'd to such a degree as to be really extended, 'tis still difficult for the imagination to break it into its component parts, because of the uneasiness it finds in the conception of such a minute object as a single point.'²

But when repeating Hume's experiment, I am unable to convince myself of his conclusion. I've drawn a dot on a piece of paper and attached it to the wall opposite me at such a distance that it is continually at the brink of disappearing from view. No doubt I've hit a limit, but what kind of limit? It seems to me that we can hardly attribute this phenomenon to something as foreign as perceptual atoms—the moment I put on my glasses, the dot becomes clear as day. With my glasses on, I can more than double the distance between myself and the piece of paper before I have trouble focusing again. The disappearance of the dot does not appear to be a result of any lower limit of perception in general, but a result of my physiology—this is not what Hume is really after.

1 Locke, *An Essay Concerning Human Understanding*, 191–93; Berkeley, *A New Theory of Vision and Other Select Philosophical Writings*, 36; Hume, *A Treatise of Human Nature*, 23.

2 Hume, *A Treatise of Human Nature*, 32.

Our visual acuity is susceptible to considerable changes over time, e.g., due to differences in lighting, the use of visual aids, monocular or binocular vision; but, if the same object taking up the same space in my visual field should now nearly disappear from view and, after putting on my glasses, be clearly defined, it seems likely that, even at the brink of disappearing, it was still an extended phenomenon composed of a multiple of these perceptual atoms. These two, physiological and experiential ‘resolution’ needn’t necessarily line up.¹ We can imagine a case in which the resolution of our experiential perception is half (or double) the size of what our physiological perception would allow, for example:

Fig. 2. Experiential half the resolution.

Fig. 3. Experiential double the resolution.

In the second case (Fig. 3), the disappearance of the dot from our sight would mark the disappearance of four perceptual atoms, not one. (And why shouldn’t it be an empirical rule that our smallest physiological sensory impression, as a physical phenomenon, has as its correlate a multitude of perceptual atoms?) It seems that Hume’s experiment doesn’t prove the existence of these atoms at all, but merely describes a causal relation between size, distance and appearance. But ‘external’ perception is not the only kind of perception and if needed we can defend Hume’s position in some other way, by looking for some other means of having acquaintance with these *minima sensibilia*. Here the imagination might help us out: though it is a possibility that our external perception never show us one such atom but only a combination, this combination nevertheless intimates the idea of a singular sense-datum. Because these singular sensations were therefore present to the mind already, we can reproduce the idea of such a singular sensible point in the imagination. However, there appear to me two further reasons for doubting the existence of these atoms:

First, phenomenologically, when looking at a coloured or shaded object, we are unable to see any separation apart from those corresponding to sudden changes in the species of colour. Compare the two figures below:

¹ “The word Sensation, to begin with, is constantly, in psychological literature, used as if it meant one and the same thing with the *physical impression* either in the terminal organs or in the centres, which is its antecedent condition, and this notwithstanding that by sensation we mean a mental, not a physical, fact.” James, *The Principles of Psychology*, 2:33–34.

Fig. 4. Black to white stepped.

Fig. 5. Black to white gradient.

If *minima sensibilia* did exist, a change in colour in Fig. 5 should correspond to a discrete change in the quality of our perceptual atoms (resembling the phenomenologically significant changes in Fig. 4)—yet we can discern no such discrete change. Similarly, when perceiving an evenly coloured surface, we cannot show where one perceptual atom stops and another begins; the entire surface is uninterrupted, without separation.

Secondly, as extension is taken to be nothing but a sum of such atoms, the Müller-Lyer illusion (Fig. 6) represents a logical impossibility. Both lines are perceived as extended, i.e., composed of a certain amount of perceptual parts. According to my perception, line 1 is shorter than line 2. This is taken to mean that line 1 is composed of fewer perceptual atoms than line 2. I now put a ruler against line 1 and measure it to be 6 cm long, i.e., the perceptual extension corresponding to 6 cm on the ruler is equal to the perceptual extension of the line. When I put the ruler against line 2, I would expect it to be longer than line 1, as line 2 is taken to be composed of more perceptual atoms than line 1; however, as we very well know, the length of line 2 will also correspond to 6 cm. This means that, as regards their perceptual extension, while line 1 does not equal line 2, both of them are equal to 6 cm.¹

Fig. 6. Müller-Lyer illusion.

These examples should make us reconsider how we conceive of the empirical relations between wholes and parts and whether a mereology which makes the whole de-

¹ As perceived on the ruler, not as an objective fact.

pendent on its parts, though such a theory is certainly appropriate for describing objects, should also be applied to experience itself.

As opposed to the above-mentioned empiricists, Kant did not believe in *minima sensibilia*. His concept of sensation in the *Critique* is hard to pin down, he gives two definitions: The first, in the *Transcendental Aesthetic*, defines sensation as ‘the effect of an object on the capacity for representation, insofar as we are affected by it’;¹ the second, in the *Doctrine of Elements*, describes it as part of a taxonomy of representation: ‘The genus is **representation** in general (*repraesentatio*). Under it stands the representation with consciousness (*perceptio*). A **perception** that refers to the subject as a modification of its state is a **sensation** (*sensatio*)’.² Neither of these are particularly clear or helpful. A more detailed description, still lacking, can be found in the *Subjective Deduction* and *Anticipations*, these will be the primary sources for my interpretation.

Sensation, as it is there described, has three main properties: It is (1) a *unity* which is (2) *unextended* in space and time (i.e., without an extensive magnitude) but which has (3) an *intensive magnitude* or degree of reality ranging from nothingness to any arbitrary size.

The *unity* of sensation is first touched upon in the *Subjective Deduction*:

‘Every intuition contains a manifold in itself, which however would not be represented as such if the mind did not distinguish the time in the succession of impressions on one another; for **as contained in one moment** no representation can ever be anything other than absolute unity.’³

And later brought up again in the *Anticipations*:

‘Apprehension, merely by means of sensation, fills only an instant (if I do not take into consideration the succession of many sensations).’⁴

His use of ‘impression’ [*Eindrücke*] indicates that we’re dealing with singular sense-data. These sensations have no extensive magnitude. Extension, (treated in the *Axioms*) would require them to be ordered in space or time, but it is only by virtue of their synthesis by the imagination, through which the understanding determines intuition in accordance with a concept, that they are given form, that they come to populate space and time; before this synthesis, they can therefore possess *no extension*.

1 Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, A19–20=B34.

2 Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, A320=B376.

3 Ibid., A99.

4 Ibid., A167=B209.

SENSATION AND EXPERIENCE

'That is, the real in appearance always has a magnitude, which is not, however, encountered in apprehension, as this takes place by means of the mere sensation in an instant and not through successive synthesis of many sensations, and thus does not proceed from the parts to the whole; it therefore has a magnitude, but not an extensive one.'¹

The *intensive magnitude* consists in a continuous degree of reality of the sensation:

'Now I call that magnitude which can only be apprehended as a unity, and in which multiplicity can only be represented through approximation to negation = 0, **intensive magnitude**. [...] Accordingly every sensation, thus also every reality in appearance, however small it may be, has a degree, i.e., an intensive magnitude'²

The distinction between extensive and intensive magnitude, rather obscure at first, becomes a lot more intelligible when we consider two examples given by Kant in the *Lectures on Metaphysics*:

'Thus, e.g., a line, which must be composed, differs from an extinguishing light: with the latter there is only a unity of sensation, but in each following state a different degree of this.'³

And:

'Therefore, e.g., a drop of boiling water is indeed *less* than a full kettle, but both are equally hot.'⁴

Intensive magnitude concerns the differences in vivacity of one and the same quality which are not related to the aggregation of different quanta, but appear to increase and diminish continuously.

The first question we should ask ourselves with regard to this theory is how we can ever know that sensations are given to the mind as unitary impressions?—Not empirically, that's for certain: never is a sensation given to us except intermingled with a great many others. 'No one has ever had a simple sensation by itself. Consciousness, from our natal day, is a seeming multiplicity of objects and relations, and what we call sensations are results of discriminative attention, pushed often to a very high degree.'⁵ Are we then to believe that we have an awareness of the synthesising act through which this multicoloured experience is established? A103–4 and B134 make claims to this end; yet in the same breath Kant seems to doubt the clarity of this awareness: 'This con-

1 Ibid., A168=B210.

2 Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, A168–69=B210–11.

3 Kant, *Lectures on Metaphysics*, 467.

4 Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, 467.

5 James, *The Principles of Psychology*, 1:224.

sciousness may often only be weak, so that we connect it with the generation of the representation only in the effect, but not in the act itself, i.e., immediately.¹ And I think that everyone can attest to the fact that we are never aware of ourselves joining the manifold sensible qualities of our experience together into relationally determined wholes. But if we place the entirety of this synthesis of unitary sensations outside of consciousness, then the synthesis itself as well as its terms (sensations) become entirely unknowable.²

However, this argument already subtly misrepresents the transcendental position which Kant either did or should have followed in his reasoning. The transcendental apperception should not be interpreted as an actual self-consciousness, nor as an unconsciousness, but purely as a necessary presupposition for the possibility of objective reality—it appears as if Kant himself loses sight of the *de jure* nature of his investigation in B134. The best way to criticise any presupposition is to show that it is entirely unnecessary; this would be the case if sensation is not really given as an unrelated manifold as Kant assumes, but is a unity or, as Ewing proposes, a unity-in-diversity.³—If what is first given to the mind is really already a complex and interrelated whole, which is the only kind of experience we are truly acquainted with, then we do not need to presuppose the existence of a pure ego.

There is another way by which the existence of sensation may be defended from a Kantian point of view, that is: by arguing from the difference between extensive and intensive magnitude. An object can either change formally, with regard to its extension and the relations of its parts, and this can be attributed to the understanding, or it can change materially, as to the vivacity of the qualities of the object—these latter changes cannot be attributed to the understanding but must be the result of something else, that is: sensation. But not only does this fail to explain why sensations should be unitary, it can also be doubted whether anything such as intensive magnitude exists at all. The concept of intensive magnitude is heavily criticised by Bergson in *Time and Free Will*⁴ and has in recent times fallen into disuse.⁵ Is the difference between a weak and a strong pain merely, as Kant claims, one of intensity, or do these phenomena actually represent different species of quality belonging to the same genus ‘pain’? E.g. pain with or without muscle tension, a burning pain, a stabbing pain, a shooting pain, and all possible combinations. And if we are dealing with the same species of quality, is the increase really intensive or is it actually extensive?—Do we experience a greater pain in the same area or is the same pain merely radiating outwards? Answering these ques-

1 Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, A103.

2 Ewing, ‘Kant’s Transcendental Deduction of the Categories’, 64.

3 Ewing, ‘Kant’s Transcendental Deduction of the Categories’, 64–65.

4 Bergson, *Time and Free Will: An Essay on the Immediate Data of Consciousness*, 1–74.

5 Michell, ‘Psychophysics, Intensive Magnitudes, and the Psychometricians’ Fallacy’.

tion is not very important at the moment so I will not discuss them any further. Even if there is such a thing as an intensive magnitude which could indicate the existence of sensation, this would not explain why sensation should be unitary as is supposed by Kant.

Both these conceptions of sensation, the empiricist's and Kantian, fall prey to Merleau-Ponty's 'experience error'¹ or James's 'psychologist's fallacy' which consist in the '*confusion of his [the psychologist's] own standpoint with that of the mental fact about which he is making his report.*'² In this case: we attribute to our consciousness of an object the properties which we intellectually know the object to possess. (A related instance of this fallacy: to attribute to our consciousness of the object our reflective knowledge of this consciousness.)

1 Merleau-Ponty, *Phenomenology of Perception*, 5.

2 James, *The Principles of Psychology*, 1:196.

PART 2
PERSONAL REFLECTIONS

Chapter 1

A Flat Ontology: The I and the Other

§18. Introduction

Like Hume, ‘when I enter most intimately into what I call *myself*¹ I never discover anything resembling an *I* or *mind*, I never discover an experiencer inside of or beside the experience—there is no seeing apart from the visual, no hearing apart from the sound, no doubting apart from the doubt, nor do I discover any experience or class of experiences which are necessarily and intimately my own. All I have direct acquaintance with are perceptions and relations. That is not to say that the world begins and ends with experience, a Berkeleian *esse est percipi* would be a bridge too far, but in the end, even our thoughts about metaphysical entities must derive their support from our experiential reality. In the following chapter I will attempt to give a sketch of my own view of mind and person, this is a continuation of the personal sections of the previous part.

I will deal with the problem of subjectivity from the perspective of an empiricist ontology. In writing this I was heavily influenced by the *radical empiricist* philosophy developed by William James in the latter part of his life. While this philosophy has not been adequately continued after James’s death, I have taken to it as an alternative to the phenomenological approach which I have lately come to reject. I will first (§19) defend my criticism of the transcendental apperception in §17 against a possible Kantian objection, this to further argue that experience does not require a pure ego. Secondly (§20), I wish to put into question our intuitive belief that there are certain experiences which are necessarily subjective, e.g., thoughts, feelings, dreams. Here I will not be arguing against a particular philosopher, but against our common way of thinking about the world. Thirdly (§21), I will address why this matters to me, what I would like to accomplish with all of this. And finally (§22), I will briefly discuss the consequences of my position on the debate on personal identity. None of the arguments of this chapter are meant to be finished, they do not answer every possible objection and I’m not yet certain that they actually correspond to the truth. Nevertheless, I am more convinced of them than of the philosophies which I aim to reject by their means and writing them out at this early stage might provide an incentive to develop them further.

1 Hume, *A Treatise of Human Nature*, 165.

§19. *The Pure Ego*

In some of the preceding sections (§§5 & 17) I've tried to criticise the Cartesian and Kantian belief in the existence of the pure ego. Now, I do not think that any of my arguments will have been particularly convincing to a proponent of these philosophies, never mind to Descartes or Kant themselves. In the case of the former, because what I denied was a matter of fact, namely that I do not experience my thoughts (in the broad Cartesian sense) as accidents which depend on some cogitative substance, my argument is easily reversible. Someone can come along and say that he *in fact* does experience this dependent nature of his thoughts and therefore has convincing grounds for believing in the existence of a substantial mind. At that point, we cannot reasonably continue to argue. In the case of the latter, a Kantian philosopher may grant that there are no unitary sensations, but claim that my unities-in-diversity still require a pure ego if they are to be connected amongst themselves. In this section I will try to defend my position against this possible objection. What I want to accomplish by criticising these theories is not to prove, once and for all, that Descartes and Kant were wrong and that my own view is the only right one. I don't believe that that is really possible and furthermore don't think that such a polemical approach is ever beneficial to philosophy. Instead, I wish to propose that the pure ego is not really necessary in philosophy, that we can do without, and that this is also a legitimate view with certain benefits.

According to Kantian philosophy, the pure ego is the logical unity which we must necessarily presuppose in the operations of the understanding: it is that which all our representations must be related to in order to be connected at all. In §17 I interpreted these 'representations' to ultimately denote sensations, that is: that the connections which the understanding establishes are either connections amongst sensations, i.e., immediately effected upon sensations, or connections amongst representations which can in the end be resolved into such immediate connections. I attempted to argue that, because the idea of unitary sensations is contrary to what is given in experience and we are unable to prove their existence, we may as well assume that what is given are those things we *do* experience, namely unities or unities-in-diversity. A Kantian philosopher may now argue, and argue quite rightfully, that, even if there are no unitary sensations, these unities-in-diversity still require a pure ego in order to be related together. Though my experience of a billiard ball is not necessarily a complex experience, the experience of two billiard balls hitting each other, and the transfer of motion from one to the other, does require there to be a certain complexity because, in the experience itself, the two billiard balls, though related, are perceived as distinct entities.

The underlying presupposition of this argument can be traced back to Hume's 'Whatever is distinct, is distinguishable; and whatever is distinguishable, is separable'.

The two billiard balls, even if they are not themselves composed of smaller parts (sensations) nevertheless are distinguishable from each other as unities-in-diversity and there is nothing in the idea of the one which implies the idea of the other. It follows that there is no *a priori* reason why, when the one hits the other, the other should start moving. According to Kant, this means that there must be something else which joins them together, in this case: the category of causation. But though I agree that we can distinguish both from each other and can imagine each one as existing separately, I do not see why this should mean that they *are* deep down separate. In the experience itself, they are experienced as related, and while, given the preceding argument, this relation is in a certain sense contingent, this contingency shouldn't affect its ability to join the two concrete phenomena together. To ask for a more real relation than the one we perceive is to ask for 'the world behind the looking-glass'.¹

Relations of causation are part of our phenomenal reality: When object A hits object B and causes it to move, we perceive B's movement as dependent on A. We *perceive* it immediately, without interruption. This presence of causation in perception was first extensively studied by Albert Michotte,² and many of his results have since been reproduced by others.³ Generally, though not necessarily, these experiments consist in showing participants multiple videos of objects in different states of movement and establishing under what circumstances the perception of causation occurs. The most researched of these causation-phenomena is the 'launching effect' (Fig. 7): one square (or rectangle) moves towards another, when they come into contact, the first square stops moving and the second square starts moving in the original direction of the first.

Fig. 7. Launching Effect

Without conscious reflection, we perceive the movement of the second as caused by the first. Some of the most interesting research on (for the most part) the launching effect was done by Alan Leslie. He focussed on the perception of causation in infants and his results indicate, on the one hand, that the perception of causation might already be present in infants 27 weeks of age,⁴ and on the other, that this experience of causation

¹ James, *The Principles of Psychology*, 1:353.

² Sadly, I've not yet had the pleasure of reading Michotte's *The Perception of Causality*.

³ Scholl and Tremoulet, 'Perceptual Causality and Animacy'.

⁴ Leslie, 'The Perception of Causality in Infants'; Leslie, 'Spatiotemporal Continuity and the Perception of Causality in Infants'; Leslie and Keeble, 'Do Six-Month-Old Infants Perceive

should not simply be equated with the experience of certain spatio-temporal properties (e.g., contact and temporal succession).¹

Other research, done by White and Milne, shows that there can be a convincing perception ('illusion') of causation even when objects are not touching each other (Fig. 8).²

Fig. 8. Pulling Effect

Now our interest in these phenomena is not to know when they occur, but simply to note *that* they occur. Their occurrence, though it can more than likely be described as a function of spatio-temporal terms, is nonetheless experienced as something distinct and existent in its own right. Of course, this is *not* the perception of causation as a universal $A \rightarrow B$, it is completely singular and particular, but it is nonetheless capable of relating experiential objects to each other.³

If it is true that such experiential relations exist, then the pure ego becomes, to a large extent, unnecessary. It is only by presupposing that experiences are originally given as unrelated that the apperception has any function. Our ability to distinguish an experience into parts does not mean that these parts are what *really* compose the experience and that the relations are added *post factum* by some faculty of understanding; we can equally well claim, without postulating anything over and above experience, that when we distinguish an experience into parts, we abstract, and in abstracting some things are lost.

§20. *The Inner and Outer*

Most of our thinking concerning subjectivity, at least in everyday life, is not about abstract entities like the pure ego, but about certain phenomena or experiential data. When we think about the subjective, we think of particular species of perception such as dreams, feelings, thoughts and imaginations, which we regard as 'inner'. Using

Causality?'

- 1 Leslie, 'Spatiotemporal Continuity and the Perception of Causality in Infants', Experiment 2; Leslie and Keeble, 'Do Six-Month-Old Infants Perceive Causality?'
- 2 White and Milne, 'Phenomenal Causality'.
- 3 Whether we can meaningfully talk about this experiential causation is another question entirely, see: Wittgenstein, *Philosophical Investigations*, 86–87.

thought-experiments, and by appealing to our pre-theoretical intuition concerning these phenomena, I would like to put into question whether this distinction between inner and outer can really be attributed to these experiences themselves.

I will begin, first, with the example of dreaming discussed by William James in Chapter VIII of *The Principles of Psychology*. He asks himself in what the relation of knowing consists and how we determine the difference between objective and subjective states of mind. How we know if something concerns the objects 'out there', common to us all, or is merely limited to a private subject of experience. Using the example of a 'clairvoyant' dream, he attempts to show that this relation of cognition may also hold of what we commonly think of as subjective states. 'Let [someone] dream the death of a certain man, and let the man simultaneously die. Is the dream a mere coincidence, or a verifiable cognition of the death?'¹ In this case, most of us (including James and myself) would consider this to be a strange coincidence, dreams are the result of psychophysical processes quite unrelated to our reliable ways of acquiring knowledge about the world and scarcely any of what we dream ever corresponds to reality. James continues,

'But if the death in the dream had a long context, agreeing point for point with every feature that attended the real death; if the subject were constantly having such dreams, all equally perfect, and if on awaking he had a habit of acting immediately as if they were true and so getting "the start" of his more tardily informed neighbors,—we should probably all have to admit that he had some mysterious kind of clairvoyant power, that his dreams in an inscrutable way knew just those realities which they figured, and that the word "coincidence" failed to touch the root of the matter.'²

And that this regularity changes matters, I think most of us would agree on as well. To maintain that these dreams were nevertheless merely inner phenomena, unrelated to outer reality, would no longer be the result a healthy and well-grounded scepticism, but would be entirely dogmatic.

Of course, to our knowledge, there is no such thing as clairvoyance, but that isn't the point of the exercise—if, in the case of the existence of these telepathic dreams, we should regard dreams as outer instead of inner experiences, then it cannot be the case that dreams are intrinsically or necessarily inner. We can develop similar examples with regard to inner thought or the imagination. If someone else were be able to, without fault and without inference from any physical phenomena, read my thoughts as I am thinking them, and is able to react to them in an appropriate manner, for ex-

1 James, *The Principles of Psychology*, 1:217.

2 Ibid., 1:218.

ample by ‘guessing’ my thoughts as a sort of test or game, then I should believe that these thoughts have become public objects.

The same goes for feelings. To me, it has always appeared as if emotions have a certain transcendence, not identical to the existence of spatio-temporal objects, but in some way comparable. When we feel lovingly, as a general disposition, we do not feel as if this emotion is exhausted by our feeling it, we do not feel as if it depends on our whims, and we do not, for that matter, feel as if this emotion is purely limited to ourselves. In this state, we believe that the world is itself beautiful, its inhabitants, every last one of them, warm and kind. If someone were to come along and tell us that we’re deluded, that everything’s bad and we’re exhausting ourselves in vain, we would think that he is mistaken—if only he’d looked better, he’d see that we’re right, that things aren’t really that bad. Of course, I’m exaggerating slightly. We do generally take the feelings of others in consideration and know that others feel differently from us. But nevertheless, when we are afraid, we do not understand how someone else can remain calm, when we enjoy something, we do not understand how others can dislike it, it’s as if they aren’t seeing things properly.

Now let’s try to imagine a world in which our emotions might not merely be private phenomena but are jointly accessible. A world where *Zeitgeist* is not used metaphorically, but where there truly is a feeling or emotion shared by all of us at any given time. We would wake up and say to our partner:

—It’s sad today.

—Oh, not again. It’s been sad since the 20th.

—Well, it couldn’t remain euphoric forever.

We could talk to each other about ‘the feeling’, as a determinate object, in the same way that we talk about the weather. Given some regularity we could use it to measure the time or to plan certain national holidays. We can continue our thought-experiment and imagine that these emotions are not actually shared by everyone simultaneously, but are located in space. The limits of their locations wouldn’t be strongly defined but, like clouds, one emotion would pass continuously into the other. Thus, we might have one stretch of space in which there is contentment and another filled with confusion. We might be moving in a certain direction and notice it getting ‘moodier’; or we could imagine that, in this alternative universe, there might be special tours dedicated to chasing different emotions. In this case, wouldn’t it be entirely possible to treat feelings as public objects for which we can define identity-conditions and to which we may attribute a spatio-temporally continuous existence? When giving directions we might say ‘straight ahead and when you pass the feeling of unease, turn right.’

Some may argue that, though in these cases joined feelings exist, each still experiences these feelings as their own. That emotions are necessarily first-personal phe-

nomena. They might say: 'I know that I feel happiness, but how do I know that others do as well?' But this either presupposes what they set out to prove, that feelings are intrinsically inner, or it is another example of the Cartesian argument that the experience requires an experiencer, which I find entirely unintelligible.

We might however reinterpret this argument and take it to mean that certainty is a mark of inner phenomena. For example, when we perceive someone whom we take to be Napoleon, we may doubt whether he really is Napoleon (as any reasonable person post-1821 should); but when we feel happy or sad, it would be absurd to ask whether we really do feel happy or sad. But though I will quite hesitantly grant the existence of such certain experiences—quite hesitantly because I believe that if we get rid of the presupposition that emotions are *for me*, then their certainty vanishes as well (see the paragraph after the next one)—I do not see why this certainty should be a mark of introspection. If we can imagine such a feeling, happiness or sadness, as an object of common discourse, shouldn't we at least consider that even these certainties might be shared with others? In our hypothetical case, they seem rather similar to other publicly observable facts.

From a Cartesian and phenomenological point of view, this certainty would not be limited to the feeling of happiness or sadness, but also extend to our hypothetical perception of Napoleon. Namely, *that* I perceive something *as* Napoleon is certain and can be interpreted as an intentional act or cogito, and this may be regarded as in a sense subjective; however, Napoleon himself, whose existence I may doubt, does not belong to my subjectivity but is the (intentional) object of this cogito.¹ But as I cannot myself discover anything resembling a *perceiving as Napoleon* apart from the (possibly mistaken) perception of Napoleon, and am wholly incapable, after many attempts at phenomenological reflection, of becoming conscious of what Husserl denotes by these intentional acts, I cannot myself agree with this description of the matter.²

My own interpretation of this presumed certainty is somewhat different: I do not believe that there is such a thing as a cogito to which the certainty should be attributed, but that this certainty is simply the result of our regarding a perception of Napoleon from the standpoint of an actual or possible corrective experience.³ When we approach it as possibly false in relation to other experiences, we imagine that what was experienced was not really Napoleon at all, but only an *as if* Napoleon. This does not mean

1 This also seem to correspond with the argument of Sydney Shoemaker in 'Self-Knowledge and "Inner Sense": Lecture I: The Object Perception Model', 260.

2 Someone exclaims, 'I can play chess!'—What in this case is the cogito? We bring him a chess set and he says, 'Chess? Oh no, not chess, I meant draughts.' We bring him draughts pieces and he is unable to make a valid move.—What was the certainty of the first cogito?

3 Perry, 'Conceptions and Misconceptions of Consciousness', 289.

that the perception which we designate an *as if*-perception is any different from the original one, but that it is differently related to our other experiences. The certainty of this *as if* is the result of the experience being taken out of every context which could prove it right or wrong, it has been declawed.

Let us imagine, finally, like Condillac, a statue cut off from the outside world to which we can choose to impart, if we want, an array of different sensations.¹ Say I give it a feeling of restlessness. Given the preceding thought-experiments, can we truly attribute to this feeling an intrinsic inwardness? Would the statue be able to identify this restlessness as its restlessness? Suppose I impart on the statue a thought of Alexander Dubček—would it know that *it* is thinking of Dubček? Personally, I do not believe this to be the case, I'm more inclined to agree with William James that the thought would simply be the statue's entire universe² and that for any meaningful distinction between the self and the world to be possible, more is needed than one momentary thought.³

If we can imagine all of this without contradiction, I do not think we should consider dreams, thoughts, feelings or imaginations as necessarily inner, but only contingently so—this is the point I want to argue. I regard it as a general mark of inner phenomena that they are private, but their privacy is established empirically,⁴ it is not an intrinsic feature of their appearance and they are not private because they are inner, but they are inner because they are private.

When someone says 'I see a church', we can turn towards the direction he is facing and realise the same perception he is having; but when he says 'I feel pain', we can look towards where he is looking, act how he is acting, stand in the same location as him, but the pain will not come. Does this mean that this pain is inner? Yes, but only because, when I act like him, I do not feel like him. There's nothing more to it.

§21. *The I and the Other*

If there is no pure ego as the correlate of every experience, and if there is no domain of experience which is necessarily subjective, then experiences are themselves, in their first appearance, impersonal. This result, though it would require further support to be of theoretical value, is at least already desirable for ethical and metaphysical reasons. In particular, I hope that it will prove a strong antidote against solipsism and egoism.

Because experience is not intrinsically *for me*, but the subjectivity of an experience consists merely in the way that it is related to other experiences, as also our experi-

1 Condillac, *Traité des sensations*, 1:5–6.

2 James, 'On the Function of Cognition', 28.

3 James, 'Does "Consciousness" Exist?', 480.

4 Bush, 'An Empirical Definition of Consciousness', 564.

ences of other people are the result of such experiential relations, there is no deep ontological divide separating the I from the other. It is of course true that certain species of experience such as dreams and feelings are generally regarded as limited to the individual that has them, but this is a purely empirical truth and is not an expression of some more fundamental metaphysical reality. Like Gurwitsch¹ and (the early) Sartre—though without relying on a phenomenological consciousness—I would like to establish ‘that the Ego is neither formally nor materially *in* consciousness: it is outside, *in the world*; it is a being in the world, like the Ego of another.’² We get to know ourselves in the same way that we get to know others: the distinction between the I and me, the self as subject and the self as object, is unwarranted, there is no self apart from the empirical self.

Though what I have said so far does not exclude the idea that human beings are necessarily egoistic or self-centred, it should make this position somewhat less attractive. We can still believe, if we want to, that deep down it is a metaphysical truth that there is an I or ego which consciously or unconsciously determines our every action, but we now have less reason to suppose this to be the case. If, however, this egoism is not meant metaphysically but descriptively, if it is taken to refer to a self-love of which we are always conscious and which motivates our actions, it must be rejected outright. When we desire something, the desire itself has no necessary *for me*-quality. It is only because others do not desire the same things as us that we do not attribute this feeling to the object itself, but this does not mean that the immediate experience of the desire presents itself as *my* desire. If it were to come about that there was an object longed for by all, or that every person always wanted the same thing as every other person, then we might be more inclined to think of desirability as an objective property.³

The rejection of the necessary subjectivity of experience is important because it ensures the *possibility* of altruistic behaviour, the *possibility* of knowing the other, the *possibility* of values inhabiting the world and the *possibility* of non-egocentric and non-anthropocentric responsibilities towards others and our environment.

§22. Consequences for Personal Identity

By rejecting the pure ego and the idea of intrinsically personal experiences, I have placed myself squarely in the empiricist camp of Locke and Hume. I will now argue that these same considerations make it impossible to say *a priori* and universally what

1 Gurwitsch, ‘A Non-Egological Conception of Consciousness’.

2 Sartre, *The Transcendence of the Ego*, 1.

3 For more arguments in support of this view, see: *Ibid.*, 13, 16–21; James, *The Principles of Psychology*, 1:317–29.

the conditions for personal identity are. We can perhaps give a vague account of what it means to us, or in our culture, but we should be wary of any theory which tries to give a more definite answer.

When we ask what it means to be a person, what we're interested in knowing is not what it means to be a particular individual, e.g., Frege or Russell, but what it means to be a person in general. Under what conditions any entity may belong to the class of persons or not. In the cases of Frege and Russell, both of whom are generally admitted to be persons and whose existence depends on their personhood, this means that answering the general question should also decide the particular ones. If Frege is a person, by which we mean that his being a person is fundamental to our identification of him as an object, then if we can explain what it means to be a person, we can explain under what circumstances Frege might exist, continue his existence, or cease to be. This, I think, everyone agrees upon. The problem lies in answering this question.

We can doubt the validity of this metaphysic of concept-dependent identification¹ given the conclusions of §17. Certainly, we do not experience ourselves as using a concept in order to individuate and determine the continued existence of an object at different points in time. But because I have not yet been able to find a better solution to this problem, except perhaps for treating our individuation of objects as primitive and therefore absolute (which I'd rather avoid), I will continue using this metaphysic for now. I even believe that this approach might yet be of some value since it corresponds to a way in which we do *act* when we are talking about objects. Though we individuate objects immediately and with little if any reflection, when we wish to know whether we are *in fact* talking about the same object, we discriminate it into its constituent parts to see whether it continues to correspond to the idea and/or knowledge we have of it. (However this knowledge may be established, whether by memory, a picture or a description.) This, however, is a different way of dealing with objects than we ordinarily do in daily life.

In the previous part, I discussed multiple views of personal identity in modern philosophy. These often differed greatly from each other: According to Descartes, for example, personal identity coincides with the identity of the immaterial substance or mind. According to Locke, it is instead a function of our memories and sensations. And according to Kant, it is the transcendental unity of apperception. In contemporary philosophy, this problem has become increasingly about whether personal identity depends on physical or psychological criteria. Wiggins claims that personal identity is a kind of numerical identity which depends on the spatio-temporally continuous existence of the living-body.² Parfit, on the other hand, believes that it is a specific identity

¹ Similar to what I described in §11.

² Wiggins, *Identity and Spatio-Temporal Continuity*, 50–51.

based on a psychological relation R of remembrance or intention.¹ But if so many answers can be given to the same question, I believe it may be valuable to see how we might go about answering this question at all.

The most natural approach is to abduce the meaning of the concept from our use of it in daily life. We should ask ourselves: When do we call something a person? But while this is no doubt a reasonable thing to do, it does not allow us to answer many of the more subtle questions, and it is these subtle questions around which the debate generally revolves. Furthermore, the answers of these various philosophers sometimes contradict our use of language, they attempt to establish how we should think about persons and not how we do, or they must decide between the self-attribution of personal identity and the attribution of personal identity by others. In all these cases, we cannot rely solely on our use of language but must look elsewhere for arguments. But where?

To a certain extent, we may have recourse to logic. This can show us what formal structure personal identity must have given certain assumptions about identity and the rough idea of person, but it will never allow us to formulate a substantial answer. That is: it can only be used to criticise inconsistencies in our concept of person and never to show what it *should* be. Neither can we turn towards experience for an answer. If we're trying to settle whether someone is still the same person after certain changes or not, we cannot point towards him and say, 'See! He's still there.' Because whether he truly is still there or not already depends on the concept we're using. This is not only true in theory, but also in practice: We see that these philosophical adversaries generally agree on the facts (actual or hypothetical) but merely debate how we should interpret them. The same states of affairs will by some be denoted a person and by others not.

That we cannot ostensibly define what it means to be a person, that it is not immediately given to us, is also what Parfit means when he says that we 'can completely describe reality without claiming that persons exist.'² But if this is admitted, then what exactly is Parfit *doing* when he criticises Williams and Wiggins? And what is Thomson *doing* when she criticises Parfit? They take the same facts but describe a different outcome. An outcome of what? Of the (correct use of the) concept 'person'. But on what basis? If we cannot have recourse to any facts in reality, how do we establish the 'correct use' of this concept in the first place? Ordinarily, when we have one word which can be used in different ways, we call it a homonym. Why not in this case? Why do they maintain that they are talking about the same thing while not talking about the same concept, nor denoting the same facts by their concepts?

If what a person is, is thought to depend on the concept we're using; and if the

1 Parfit, *Reasons and Persons*, 215–17. See also: Parfit, 'Personal Identity', 20.

2 Parfit, *Reasons and Persons*, 213.

meaning of this concept should cause one philosopher to call something a person which another does not; and if we cannot turn towards experience to settle which use is correct, but instead, what is or is not a person depends solely on these concepts themselves; then these philosophers, though they use the same words are simply not talking about the same concepts, and by extension, the same objects. If this is true, then every one of their arguments is a paralogism, a *Sophisma figurae dictionis*.¹ They are not talking to, but past each other. At first sight, Parfit's way of reasoning appears to avoid this problem by not making his argument about what a person is, but about *what matters* in personal identity, psychologically, emotionally.² His question is: 'When do we feel that we are justified in calling someone the same person despite the indeterminacy and contingency of this concept?' This, however, helps very little. On the one hand, exactly 'what matters' is not universally agreed upon. For example, Judith Thomson uses the same 'what matters'-argument in defence of her own physical view and to criticise Parfit's neo-Lockean idea of person.³ On the other, what matters in personal identity surely depends on what we believe personal identity to be in the first place. In the same way that we cannot say what matters in chess without taking into consideration the rules of chess, we cannot say what matters in personal identity without taking into account what it means to be a person.

It follows that to the question, 'What does it mean to be a person?', I can give no definite answer. Given the present metaphysic, what a person is, is simply a combination of facts picked out by a concept. To this same word many concepts may be attached, and for the purposes of daily life, the uses of these concepts will often coincide—whether we use physical or psychological criteria generally does not matter as we often manage to pick out the same entities by their means—and this leads us to believe that we are talking about the same thing. If then our questions become more sophisticated and subtle, and disagreements become noticeable, we should not continue to maintain that we are in fact talking about the same thing and that consequently one or both of us must be wrong, but that we weren't or aren't talking about the same thing at all and have misunderstood each other's uses of this word. What mars our thinking in this instance, what convinces us that we are talking about the same thing despite our differences, is plainly Bacon's familiar idol of the marketplace.

This ambiguity also affects our thinking about non-persons, only in these cases we are less bothered by it. We do not believe that it is strange that the existence or cessation of a particular may be arbitrary. We do not always know whether some political party, as it exists now, is truly the same as one that existed in the past; whether World

1 A sophism of figure of speech. See: Kant, *Critique of Pure Reason*, B411.

2 Parfit, *Reasons and Persons*, 241.

3 Thomson, 'People and Their Bodies', 169.

CONCLUDING SECTION

War II began in 1937 with the Marco Polo Bridge Incident, or in 1939 with the German invasion of Poland; whether two trees, when ornately grafted onto each other, are then still two or become one. Our answer depends on the criteria we're using. The difference between personal and non-personal identity is that we find it difficult to believe that whether someone lives or dies depends on something as inconsequential as the meaning of a concept. That someone may be the same person under one concept but different or non-existent under another. But if the debate on personal identity is anything to go by, this is exactly what does happen. The exact same facts lead to different outcomes.¹

If we believe, as William James does, that any experience is 'virtually or potentially either object or subject',² we should not take this to mean that there is still a predestined sense in which it can still be object or subject, that being an object remains essentially different from being a subject. We should leave behind our metaphysical belief that this distinction is profoundly meaningful. Though a rose may be a rose may be a rose—it never really *is* a rose. This is exactly Shakespeare's point. It *needn't be* a rose. There's nothing in the entirety of its appearance which destines it to this fate, there is no original sign or symbol. (The order of words is not the order of beings!) This reasoning should be extended beyond the existence of objects towards that of subjects.

§23. *Concluding Section*

My paper has been a first attempt at figuring out what the self is. It is part interpretative, part essayistic. On the one hand, I've tried to get a better idea of the role of the self or subject in Western philosophy. To better understand why the self matters and how or where it can be discovered. Due to the prohibitive length of my paper, I had to be selective in the philosophers I could reasonably discuss. I believe that, with regard to the subject I'm dealing with, Descartes, Locke, Hume and Kant provide a good starting point. Each of them has greatly influenced our thinking about self and subjectivity and their philosophies remain relevant to this day.

On the other hand, I've engaged with these philosophers in order to criticise or further develop the diverse notions of self which they put forward. Throughout all these personal sections, I've tried to consistently argue against the inherent subjectivity of experience and this is to me the most important theme of this paper. However, most of my arguments remain provisional and unfinished, and multiple smaller ideas lay strewn throughout these pages. While I wish to develop most of these ideas further, there is no single one in which I'm entirely confident. Despite this, I hope that the

1 Not different states of affairs, but the individuation of different objects.

2 James, 'Does "Consciousness" Exist?', 485.

reader may be able to discover something of value in this paper, if not in my personal sections, then perhaps in my interpretations on which I spent a lot of time and effort.

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